

Inherit

Second wave of INHERIT Decision support services/D4.2

WP 4, T 4.1 – 4.4

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Technical references

Project Acronym	INHERIT
Project Title	Next Generation Solutions for Sustainable, Inclusive, Resource-efficient and Resilient Cultural Heritage
Project Coordinator	Stamatia Rizou SingularLogic S.A. srizou@singularlogic.eu
Project Duration	October 2023 – September 2027 (42 months)

Deliverable No.	D4.1
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 4 – Decision support services for the heritage-built environment’s life cycle
Task	T4.1 – Smartification and data exchange platform, tailored to CH and compliant with European Data Spaces T4.2 – ‘Design & renovation’ services T4.3 – ‘Monitoring, operation & management’ services T4.4 – ‘Preservation & maintenance’ services
Lead beneficiary	SLG
Contributing beneficiary/ies	UPRC, ICCS, CARTIF, UU, CEMOSA, UCL
Due date of deliverable	31 August 2025
Actual submission date	29 August 2025

* PU = Public -fully open

SEN = Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

v	Date	Beneficiary	Author	Contribution
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1.1	30/06/2025	ICCS, CARTIF, UPRC, UCL, UU, CEMOSA	Evangelos Spiliotis (ICCS), Carla Rodriguez Alonso, Maria Esteban Ferrer, Victor Ivan Serna Gonzalez (CARTIF), Dimitra Tzani (UPRC), Weiwei Chen (UCL),	Input for the service overview, input and output data, architecture, and deployment of the services

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3.0	17/08/2025	RPR, UU, BYCN	GAUVIN Xavier (BYCN), Heracles Polatidis (UU)	Internal Review
4.0	27/08/2025	SLG	Iasonas Sotiropoulos, Antonia Vronti (SLG)	Final Consolidation of D4.2

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
3D	Three dimensions
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
BGI	Blue-Green Infrastructure
BIM	Building Information Model
BVC	Building's Value Chain
CDH	Cooling Degree Hours
CGAL	Computational Geometry Algorithms Library
CH	Cultural Heritage
CityGML	City Geography Markup Language
CMIP6	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6
D	Deliverable
DBSCAN	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
DB	Database
DT	Digital Twin
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
EGNSS	European Global Navigation Satellite System
EOSC	European open Science Cloud
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
FDAM	Flood Damage Assessment Methodology
GA	Grant Agreement
gDT	geometric Digital Twin
GIS	Geographical Information System
GNNS	Graph Neural Networks

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Acronym	Description
GPS	Global Positioning System
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IQR	Interquartile Range
IEQ	Indoor Environmental Quality
ML	Machine Learning
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport.
OIDC	OpenID Connect.
REST API	Representational State Transfer – Application Programming Interface
SPP	Serial Port Profile
T	Task
UI	User Interface
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This deliverable (D) provides the second iteration of **INHERIT’s decision support services**, as developed under Work Package 4 (WP4). It captures the ongoing **technical design, architectural refinement, and functional integration** of services supporting the full life cycle of heritage-built environments. The document consolidates updates across all four core tasks of WP4, detailing progress on the Smartification and Data Exchange Platform, design and renovation tools, monitoring and operation services, and preservation and maintenance components.

Building on the initial release, this version integrates **technical enhancements, updated service specifications, and early feedback** from internal testing and stakeholder engagement. It presents an updated conceptual architecture, outlines the interaction between components, and includes a consolidated view of the current development status of each service.

The deliverable also introduces tools and templates used to align contributions across partners and sets out the roadmap for the final release, highlighting incremental improvements and priorities for further development and validation.

1. Introduction

The preservation of Cultural Heritage (CH) remains a cornerstone of European identity, creativity, and sustainable development. As outlined in the first deliverable, the INHERIT project aims to address the complex challenges of managing the heritage-built environment by developing modular, interoperable, and user-centric digital solutions. These solutions leverage cutting-edge technologies—including Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and data spaces—to ensure that cultural heritage assets not only endure but continue to enrich urban environments.

This second deliverable presents the evolution and refinement of the initial architecture, services, and technological components defined in WP4: *“Decision Support Services for the Heritage-Built Environment’s Life Cycle.”* It builds upon the foundational work described in the first release, incorporating new developments, feedback from initial evaluations, and expanded functionality across multiple services.

WP4 is structured around the design and deployment of ICT-based tools and services that support decision-making across the full life cycle of CH assets, ranging from design and renovation to monitoring, maintenance, and operation. These services are aligned with European data interoperability initiatives and designed to be modular, scalable, and adaptable to a range of CH contexts.

This document includes updates and new findings across the following key tasks:

- **Task 4.1:** Refinement and extension of the **Smartification and Data Exchange Platform (s.0)**, now featuring improved modularity and enhanced data handling
- **Task 4.2:** Continued development of **Design & Renovation Services (s.1, s.2, s.3)**, with expanded support for data-driven simulations and early-stage intervention planning.
- **Task 4.3:** Progress at the **Monitoring, Operation & Management Services (s.4, s.5, s.6, s.7)**, including updated real-time and historical monitoring capabilities, and intelligent analytics.
- **Task 4.4:** Further enhancement of **Preservation & Maintenance Services (s.8, s.9, s.10)**.

In addition to updated architectural components and technical refinements, this version documents the outcomes of internal testing, user feedback, and initial validation activities, offering insights into the evolving integration of INHERIT’s platform and services.

This deliverable also outlines the updated roadmap toward the third and final release, including clear progress indicators for each functional component, as well as the incremental improvements introduced in this iteration. Through this continuous development process, INHERIT remains committed to delivering robust, effective, and future-ready digital services that empower all stakeholders involved in cultural heritage management.

1.1. Deliverable structure

The present D4.2 “Second wave INHERIT Decision support services” is the second iteration of the decision support services for the heritage-built environment’s life cycle. The document is structured in the following sections:

- **Section 1**, the current section, introduces the INHERIT project, WP4’s objectives and concept, services, as well as its methodology.
- **Section 2**, presents and describes the development related to T4.1 so far, and more specifically, of the service s.0 Data Exchange Platform for CH buildings.
- **Section 3**, presents the progress of T4.2, that includes the ‘Design & Renovation’ services (s.1 – s.3)
- **Section 4**, presents the progress of T4.3, which includes the ‘Monitoring, Operation & Management’ services (s.4 – s.7)
- **Section 5**, presents the progress of T4.4, which includes the ‘Preservation & Maintenance’ services (s.8 – s.10)

1.2. Updated Conceptual Architecture

The updated conceptual architecture, presented in Figure 1, illustrates a modular and layered data platform designed to **support secure, scalable, and real-time data exchange**. On the left, the Identity Provisioning component ensures that all services and data transactions are authenticated and authorized, establishing a secure foundation. At the bottom layer, sensor data is incorporated into the platform via an MQTT Broker, which enables lightweight, real-time data streaming from distributed sources. **This dynamic data is stored in a SQL database**, while previous versions or aggregated snapshots of the database are periodically offloaded to the data storage layer for backup and historical analysis. In parallel, user static data—including building metadata, configuration files, or manually uploaded datasets— is also persisted within the data storage layer. The latter aggregates all incoming and static data, serving as a unified data backbone. In addition, two key access interfaces are defined: **a Realtime API**, which supports on-demand, low-latency data access, **and a data portal**, which provides more structured and user-friendly access for exploration and visualization. The real-time API is mainly used by the services of T4.3 — Monitoring, Operation & Management Services— while the rest of the services that do not require real-time data retrieval can use the API provided by the data portal. This separation of concerns supports extensibility and maintainability while maintaining performance and data integrity across the system.

Figure 1: Conceptual Architecture of the INHERIT ICT Platform

1.3. Technology releases delivery

Table 1 depicts the different developments of the services that will be offered by the INHERIT project. The “Key Features” column lists the different functionalities of the services that are delivered in the second iteration of the INHERIT toolkit.

Type: 1-Web Service; 2-Infrastructure; 3-BIM Models; 4-Algorithms; 5-Datasets

Tool	Type	Key features for the 2 nd iteration of the INHERIT services
s.0 Data Exchange Platform	2-Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finalized architecture Handling both real-time and static data storage Data portal and APIs developed and deployed
s.1 Interactive screen use and AR VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction	1- Web service 5-Datasets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delivery of real-time AR/VR Immersive Interaction
s.2 Modeling and simulation environment	1-Web service 5-Datasets and renovation roadmaps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Baseline model development Data collected

Tool	Type	Key features for the 2 nd iteration of the INHERIT services
s.3 Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	1-Web service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Updated architecture ▪ Baseline developments for pilot testing
s.4 Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimization	1- Web Service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Developed Modular and Scalable Architecture ▪ Implemented Automated Deployment & Testing ▪ Structured Layered Design
s.5 Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	1- Web service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Finalized architecture ▪ Development of frontend application ▪ Anomaly detection
s.6 Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real time monitoring and management	1- Web service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Finalized architecture ▪ Development of initial UI interfaces
s.7 Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	1- Web service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Finalized architecture ▪ Deployed tool with synthetic data ▪ Almost-ready User Interface
s.8 Preventive Maintenance with H-BIM	3- BIM Models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Federated HBIM architecture ▪ Structured data modelling ▪ Embedded user interaction
s.9 GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	1- Web service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Developed and Implemented Data Preparation ▪ Implemented Interactive Feature Layers ▪ Developed Custom User Interface
s.10 Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	1-Web service 5-Maps and datasets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Consolidated Core Backend Components ▪ Developed Interactive Frontend Interface ▪ Prepared for Full Integration

Table 1: Developments and Key Features of the 2nd Release of the INHERIT Solutions

2. Smartification and data exchange platform, tailored to CH and compliant with European Data Spaces

2.1. Updated Architecture

The updated architecture of the data exchange platform introduces a secure, modular, and extensible design that supports real-time data acquisition, storage, cataloguing, and discovery. At the core of the system lies a Data Portal, which acts as the central service, through which users interact with the platform. Identity provisioning is delegated to a service that follows the OIDC principles, namely Keycloak, which ensures secure identity and access management across all services via standardized protocols. Once authenticated, users can access the CKAN interface to browse, upload, or search for datasets.

CKAN, acting as the Data Portal, interacts with a custom user interface tailored to the platform's domain needs. Underneath, CKAN communicates with an S3-compatible object storage backend, provided by MinIO. This setup allows for the efficient storage and retrieval of dataset resources, while metadata and indexing operations are handled by CKAN's internal API. In parallel, the platform integrates with IoT infrastructure through an MQTT broker. Sensors deployed in the environment publish data to MQTT topics, which are consumed by a backend API service. This service subscribes to relevant topics, parses the incoming messages, and stores structured data into a PostgreSQL database for persistent storage and analysis. The same API also performs regular backups of the ingested data into MinIO, maintaining consistency between real-time and archival storage.

This architecture, presented in Figure 2, reflects a modern, scalable approach to urban and building data management. It facilitates secure user access, real-time sensor data collection, and long-term storage, while maintaining full interoperability between components and offering a foundation for further integration with digital twin systems or advanced analytics.

Figure 2: Updated architecture of the Data Exchange Platform

2.2. Real-time data storage

The real-time data storage plays an instrumental role in the overall architecture. Using a PostgreSQL database and leveraging its key characteristics, such as efficient read/write operations, robustness, and promoted structure, has served as the persistent layer of the data efficiently produced by the MQTT sensors.

The generated data from the MQTT sensors is first piped through a backend consumer service, where a preprocess operation takes place. By applying this operation, the data are transformed into the necessary structure for database persistence. The database is not exposed publicly to the internet, but an admin tool is utilized, namely pgAdmin, and is presented in Figure 3.

Some of the developed services heavily rely on historical data, so the data storage needs to have some kind of guarantee that the data is always accessible, and, in case of an incident, any data loss is minimized. For this reason, a full backup of the entire database, containing both the data and the user/role, has been scheduled every week. An automated bash script was created which connects to the database, performs a dump operation, compresses the produced .sql file using industry standard compression algorithms, and uploads it to the static data storage, which will be described in the following section.

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Figure 3: Accessing the INHERIT database via pgAdmin

2.3. Static data storage

A critical component of the updated data management platform is the static data storage, designed to serve the long-term needs of the INHERIT ecosystem. This component addresses the storage, delivery, and preservation of all static files that are essential for the operation of the services across the ecosystem. The static data storage is based on an open-source, high-performance, S3-compatible object storage solution, namely MinIO. This choice ensures compatibility with modern cloud-native architectures while offering flexibility for both on-premise and cloud deployments.

In more detail, leveraging MinIO, the static data storage provides a scalable solution for efficient and agnostic storage. MinIO is an open-source software that is built for high-performance object storage, utilizing parallelization techniques and horizontal scalability by adding new nodes to the cluster. In addition, it provides various security features, including encryption in transit and at rest, as well as the support of secure communication protocols. Its nature ensures scalability, reliability, and high availability, aligning with the platform's commitment to data integrity. In addition, its built-in type of agnosticism aligns with the platform's commitment to handling diverse data types efficiently. MinIO is accessible at <https://minio-inherit.euinno.eu/>, and is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: INHERIT buckets in MinIO, dedicated to the Data Exchange Platform

2.4. Data Portal

At the core of the INHERIT data management architecture lies Data Portal, a customized instance of CKAN, a well-known and widely adopted software. The portal, available at <https://datamanager-inherit.euinno.eu/> and shown below in Figure 5, serves as the primary gateway for discovering, accessing, and publishing datasets relevant to the INHERIT ecosystem. It enables end-users and programmatic agents to interact with a wide range of structured and unstructured data, while maintaining strict authentication, metadata quality, and interoperability standards.

Figure 5: CKAN instance, acting as the Data Portal of the Data Exchange Platform

Metadata plays a central role in ensuring that datasets within the INHERIT ecosystem are not only findable and accessible, but also interoperable. CKAN provides a structured and user-friendly metadata interface that supports both standard descriptors. Each dataset can be described using a comprehensive set of metadata, including a title, a rich-text description with Markdown formatting, thematic tags, and licensing information. These fields enhance searchability, provide context, and clarify the legal terms for reuse. Datasets are associated with specific organizations within the portal, enabling organizational ownership, filtering, and access control. Visibility options allow datasets to be marked as public or private, depending on their intended availability. Additional metadata fields capture information about the data source, version, author, maintainer, and contact details, supporting provenance, attribution, and responsibility. To accommodate domain-specific needs, the portal also supports the use of custom fields, which can hold information such as simulation scenario IDs, building references, sensor groupings, or other INHERIT-relevant annotations.

Data exchange within the Data Portal is designed to support flexible and secure collaboration between organizations and users. Dataset owners can choose to make a dataset publicly accessible by switching its visibility setting from private to public, allowing any authenticated or anonymous user to access and reuse the data. Alternatively, for controlled data sharing, collaborators can be added directly to a dataset or an organization, granting them specific permissions such as viewing, editing, or managing the dataset without exposing it to the wider public. This approach enables organizations to maintain privacy and data ownership while facilitating organizational cooperation.

The CKAN instance has been specifically configured to integrate with MinIO and Keycloak, forming a secure and scalable platform for managing urban and environmental datasets. User authentication is fully handled by Keycloak, which has been integrated into CKAN through a custom-developed plugin. This plugin supports single sign-on (SSO) and role-based access control, ensuring that only authorized users can access protected datasets or perform administrative actions. This allows the portal to align with the broader identity and access management policies of the INHERIT ecosystem. Additionally, MinIO serves as the backend object storage for large static files such as geospatial datasets and BIM models (see Section 2.3). Files uploaded via the portal are stored in MinIO, while their metadata and access policies are managed through CKAN's internal system. This design allows CKAN to remain the main access point and single authority for all resources, while delegating efficient storage and retrieval to the underlying S3-compatible data storage.

Furthermore, the portal includes several plugins that enhance its usability and functionality by enabling in-browser previews of uploaded files, supporting formats such as CSV, GeoJSON, and image files (Figure 6). This allows users to quickly inspect dataset contents before downloading or using them in analytical workflows. These previews are particularly useful in contexts where quick evaluation of content is necessary, such as during cross-organizational collaboration or field validation.

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Grid Graph Map 9622 records « 1 - 0 » Search data ... Go » Filters

_id	room_name	floor_id	measurement_key	unit_name	measurement	timestamp
339854	Conference ...	2	AbsolutePressure	None	1009.7	2025-05-23T07:59:37
361283	Office 2	1	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.7	2025-05-23T07:59:36
313181	Seminar Room	0	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.4	2025-05-23T07:54:47
353435	Office	2	AbsolutePressure	None	1008.9	2025-05-23T07:52:32
326501	Hallway	1	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.9	2025-05-23T07:51:10
305516	Exhibition Hall	0	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.6	2025-05-23T07:11:35
313182	Seminar Room	0	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.4	2025-05-23T06:59:32
361284	Office 2	1	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.7	2025-05-23T06:59:10
339855	Conference ...	2	AbsolutePressure	None	1009.7	2025-05-23T06:58:55
305517	Exhibition Hall	0	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.4	2025-05-23T06:56:27
326502	Hallway	1	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.8	2025-05-23T06:52:09
353436	Office	2	AbsolutePressure	None	1008.8	2025-05-23T06:52:01
361285	Office 2	1	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.7	2025-05-23T05:58:40
339856	Conference ...	2	AbsolutePressure	None	1009.6	2025-05-23T05:58:25
313183	Seminar Room	0	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.3	2025-05-23T05:53:40
326503	Hallway	1	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.8	2025-05-23T05:51:16
353437	Office	2	AbsolutePressure	None	1008.8	2025-05-23T05:50:55
361286	Office 2	1	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.7	2025-05-23T04:58:11
339857	Conference ...	2	AbsolutePressure	None	1009.7	2025-05-23T04:57:58
326504	Hallway	1	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.8	2025-05-23T04:55:12
313184	Seminar Room	0	AbsolutePressure	None	1010.3	2025-05-23T04:53:08
353438	Office	2	AbsolutePressure	None	1008.8	2025-05-23T04:50:21
353439	Office	2	AbsolutePressure	None	1008.7	2025-05-23T03:59:54

Filters
Add filter
measurement_key x
AbsolutePressure
Update

(a) Grid in-browser preview of tabular data

(b) Graph in-browser preview of tabular data

Figure 6: In-browser preview examples

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The data portal is not only designed for human interaction but also supports programmatic access. Each registered user can generate API tokens (Figure 7), which grant secure access to CKAN's REST API. Through this interface, users and external applications can search for datasets, download resources, upload new data, or integrate CKAN with external systems such as digital twins, context brokers, or AI pipelines. The token-based authentication mechanism provides an efficient alternative to browser-based access and is compatible with standard HTTP requests.

Figure 7: Token creation for remote data management

Together, these features make the Data Portal a central pillar of the INHERIT data infrastructure. It provides a transparent and interoperable environment for data discovery and access, supporting a wide range of services. Its extensibility ensures that the portal can evolve alongside the needs of the project, integrating new data types, services, and user groups as the project progresses.

3. ‘Design & renovation’ services

3.1. s.1 Interactive screen use and AR VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction

3.1.1. Service overview

The maintenance and renovation of cultural heritage buildings face significant challenges globally. These include the lack of accurate and up-to-date documentation, limited accessibility for detailed inspections, and difficulties in engaging stakeholders throughout the planning process. A particular challenge lies in the inability to effectively visualise and compare before-and-after renovation scenarios, making it difficult to assess the potential impacts of different interventions on the heritage structure and its historical value. Additionally, maintenance and renovation activities often risk damaging fragile historical structures due to a lack of contextual awareness on-site. Addressing these challenges requires advanced tools that can support precise planning, effective stakeholder collaboration, and informed decision-making while ensuring the protection and sustainability of cultural heritage.

The main aim of the service is to provide VR- and AR-based solutions for the building design and renovation construction of the cultural heritage buildings, including 1) AR-based maintenance and renovation to improve work quality and reduce maintenance and renovation time, 2) AR-based human-machine interaction to support on-the-job training, and 3) VR-based pre-intervention planning. VR facilitates in-depth exploration of cultural heritages, allowing different stakeholders to engage from multiple perspectives and improving the efficiency of planning and execution. Meanwhile, AR enhances accessibility and provides site staff with an effective means to showcase key elements and areas of interest with minimal effort. The service will be applied to Pilot 5 (Poland) and Pilot 6 (Spain) to support the finding of optimal renovation solutions.

The overall methodology is presented in Figure 8. To achieve the goals, the AR/VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction can be implemented following four main steps:

1. Raw data acquisition, including the Building Information Modelling (BIM) data for the heritage buildings and their relevant information, such as heating or ventilation systems.
2. Construction of a VR scenario that will allow for interactions by different stakeholders and the presentation of renovation strategies.
3. Construction of an AR scenario, which can enable human-machine interaction and analysis for the renovation strategies.
4. Pilot application to find the optimum renovation solutions for Pilot 5 and Pilot 6.

Figure 8: Overall methodology of the interactive screen use and AR/VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction

3.1.2. Input & output data

Input Data

1. **BIM data:** Comprehensive details about the building's architecture, structural components, materials, and other relevant attributes, providing a digital representation of the heritage building for integration into AR/VR environments.
2. **Sensor data:** Real-time environmental monitoring data collected from sensors installed in the heritage buildings within Pilot 5 (Poland) and Pilot 6 (Spain). This includes parameters such as temperature, humidity, pressure, absolute pressure, noise, and CO₂ levels, enabling accurate representation of environmental conditions during renovation planning and on-site execution.
3. **Maintenance/renovation strategies:** Predefined renovation and maintenance plans developed for the pilot sites, including proposed interventions, timelines, and resource allocations, which are used for simulation and visualisation within AR and VR environments to compare before-and-after scenarios and evaluate the impacts of different renovation options.
4. **Regulatory and conservation guidelines:** Relevant local regulations, heritage conservation guidelines, and restrictions that need to be considered during renovation planning to ensure interventions comply with preservation standards.
5. **Photogrammetry and point cloud data (optional):** High-resolution images and 3D point cloud scans captured on-site to enhance the fidelity of the AR/VR models and to support the assessment of the current conditions of the heritage structures.

Output Data

1. **Integrated heritage management platform:** A comprehensive platform is provided, serving as a centralized hub that consolidates all relevant information and tools required for effective heritage management and execution. The platform includes:

- a. Service descriptions outlining capabilities and workflows;
 - b. Pilot site descriptions with specific heritage and intervention details;
 - c. BIM models and point cloud data for detailed digital representations;
 - d. Before-and-after renovation scenario comparisons to support evidence-based decision-making;
 - e. Maintenance information for potential structural defects.
2. Augmented Reality-based renovation scenario visualisation and comparison: AR overlays enable the visualisation of before-and-after renovation scenarios directly on-site, allowing stakeholders to intuitively assess the impacts of proposed interventions on heritage structures. This facilitates informed decision-making during the planning phase, enhancing transparency and supporting collaboration between conservators, engineers, and authorities. The AR environment further enables interactive engagement, allowing users to explore specific elements and areas of interest and receive context-sensitive information with minimal effort.
 3. Virtual Reality-based renovation process simulation: VR environments replicate the entire renovation process, enabling stakeholders and maintenance personnel to visualise and understand each stage of the intervention before physical implementation. This supports on-the-job training, familiarising workers with specific tasks, safety procedures, and the sequence of operations, thereby reducing on-site errors and preserving the integrity of heritage structures during renovation.
 4. Environmental condition-integrated monitoring: By integrating real-time sensor data (temperature, humidity, CO₂, noise, pressure) into AR/VR environments, the system provides a dynamic and accurate representation of the heritage building's environmental conditions. This helps stakeholders understand how environmental factors may impact renovation strategies and assists in planning interventions that are sensitive to the conservation needs of heritage structures.

3.1.3. Updated architecture & technical specification

In this service, the system architecture is designed with three main layers: the physical layer, data layer, and application layer. Each layer works in tandem with the others to ensure the efficient operation and management of the heritage building project. The system architecture is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: The architecture of the service

1. The physical layer forms the foundation of the system and includes AR and VR devices, as well as various sensors installed within the building. AR devices, such as Microsoft HoloLens 2, provide augmented reality experiences that support on-the-job training and maintenance tasks directly on-site. VR devices offer immersive virtual environments for building showcases and other virtual activities. Additionally, sensors within the building monitor real-time conditions, such as temperature, humidity, and energy consumption, providing essential data to the data layer.
2. The data layer serves as the system's core, integrating multiple data sources, including BIM data covering structural components and attribute information, energy consumption data, and environmental sensor data. This layer not only supports the applications used in the system but also provides real-time and historical data for decision-making. BIM data is particularly important, as it contains detailed information about the building's structure, design, maintenance records, and material specifications. This comprehensive dataset underpins the AR and VR applications, ensuring they are accurate and contextually relevant.
3. The application layer is where the different stakeholders interact with the system's capabilities, encompassing various AR and VR-based application modules. VR technology enables users to explore the heritage building in a virtual environment, allowing for a more intuitive understanding of its history and evolution. AR-based applications are used for on-the-job training, providing staff with real-time guidance and feedback in their actual work environments, thus improving efficiency and safety. Additionally, AR is

employed in maintenance and renovation tasks, helping maintenance personnel identify and address issues more effectively, which optimizes maintenance processes. The application layer ensures that all interactions are user-centric, focusing on enhancing the experiences and outcomes for the stakeholders involved, and the optimal renovation solutions can be found.

Figure 10 presents the tech stack for the AR/VR interface development.

Figure 10: The tech stack for the AR/VR interface development

The figure illustrates the technical architecture of the AR/VR-based heritage renovation platform. At the core, the system is built on the Unity engine using C#, providing a flexible and powerful environment for AR/VR application development. On top of this, AR/VR SDKs and APIs such as SteamVR and XR Plugin Management are integrated to enable cross-platform immersive experiences.

Above this layer, the system incorporates four key modules:

1. UI and interaction library: Utilising Unity UI Toolkit, Json.NET, and Photoshop to design and implement intuitive and responsive user interfaces.
2. Data management and integration: Leveraging SQLite/NoSQL databases and RESTful APIs to manage and integrate BIM models, sensor data, and renovation plans seamlessly.
3. Graphics and rendering: Using ShaderLab and post-processing stacks to enhance visual fidelity and ensure realistic rendering within AR/VR environments.
4. Version control: Git is employed for maintaining version control, ensuring collaborative and systematic development practices across the team.

This modular and layered architecture enables efficient development, seamless data integration, and high-fidelity AR/VR visualisation, supporting the effective delivery of heritage renovation planning and training services within the platform.

3.1.4. Implementation: second technology release

The backend of the AR/VR-based heritage renovation platform is designed to ensure efficient data management, seamless integration of multimodal data sources, and scalable processing of heritage-specific information, while supporting real-time delivery of this data to the frontend for interactive visualisation and user engagement through custom-designed AR and VR interfaces. This architecture allows users to access, visualise, and interact with complex BIM models, sensor data, and renovation scenarios intuitively within the AR/VR environments

3.1.4.1. Backend implementation

The backend of the AR/VR-based heritage renovation platform is implemented through the Unity engine using C#, which serves as the backbone for data handling, processing, and management within the AR/VR environments, as illustrated in Figure 11.

For the Integrated Heritage Management Platform, after importing HBIM models, custom C# scripts are developed within Unity to enable multiple functionalities, including viewing the heritage building from different perspectives, accessing and displaying maintenance information, and comparing before-and-after renovation scenarios in the platform. Some of the scripts are shown in Figure 11. These functionalities allow stakeholders to interactively explore heritage data and renovation plans, supporting evidence-based decision-making throughout the planning and execution phases.

For environmental monitoring, data collected from on-site sensors are stored in a structured database, ensuring organised and secure data management. API interfaces are developed to facilitate continuous and controlled access to the data, allowing real-time retrieval for analysis and display within AR/VR environments. The data are visualised according to time and category (e.g., temperature, humidity, CO₂ levels, noise, pressure), enabling stakeholders to monitor environmental conditions that may affect the heritage building and to consider these conditions when planning maintenance and renovation interventions.

Building upon the integrated heritage management platform, an AR application is developed to extend key functionalities into on-site, immersive environments. The AR development environment is first established using the Mixed Reality Toolkit (MRTK), enabling cross-device AR deployment and intuitive user interaction design. Development is conducted within Unity using C#, where the functionalities from the platform—maintenance information access, renovation scenario comparison, and environmental monitoring visualisation—are adapted and presented within the AR environment.

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ArrowClickHandler.cs	2025/2/18 3:07	C# Source File	4 KB
ArrowIndicator.cs	2024/12/4 18:02	C# Source File	4 KB
Before renovation.cs	2024/12/10 18:18	C# Source File	4 KB
CameraRotate.cs	2025/2/17 18:25	C# Source File	2 KB
FlagClick.cs	2025/2/17 11:55	C# Source File	5 KB
Pilot Application.cs	2025/2/17 11:55	C# Source File	2 KB
PointCloudPhotoViewer.cs	2024/11/25 14:31	C# Source File	2 KB
PolandPointCloud.cs	2025/2/17 23:21	C# Source File	2 KB
PolandUIChange.cs	2025/2/17 22:47	C# Source File	2 KB
RenoInfor.cs	2024/12/4 17:00	C# Source File	2 KB
RenoScenarios.cs	2024/12/4 21:05	C# Source File	2 KB
ShowRenovationPanel.cs	2024/12/4 19:48	C# Source File	1 KB
V2 Maintenance info.cs	2025/2/18 1:48	C# Source File	2 KB
V2 RenoScenario.cs	2025/2/20 11:55	C# Source File	4 KB
V2 View change.cs	2025/2/17 22:25	C# Source File	3 KB
ViewChange.cs	2024/11/13 16:22	C# Source File	3 KB
ViewPolandDetails.cs	2025/2/17 20:45	C# Source File	2 KB

Figure 11: Part of the C# scripts in the platform

3.1.4.2. Frontend implementation

The frontend of the AR/VR-based heritage renovation platform focuses on delivering an intuitive, interactive, and visually clear user experience. The interface design is developed using Adobe Photoshop (PS) for graphic asset creation and Unity’s UGUI system for interface layout and implementation.

Figure 12 presents the UI interface for the integrated management platform. Figure 12a, 12b, and 12c illustrate the integrated platform, showcasing the service overview, maintenance information, and before-and-after renovation scenarios, respectively. Users can interact with the platform to access and explore these different information layers, facilitating informed decision-making and efficient management within heritage renovation projects.

(a) Service overview and pilot descriptions

(b) Maintenance information

Figure 12: User interface of the integrated management platform

Based on this integrated platform, an AR application has been developed to extend these functionalities into immersive, on-site environments prior to onsite deployment. Figure 13a–c presents the corresponding information within the AR environment, showcasing how maintenance information, renovation scenarios, and environmental monitoring data are visualised contextually. User interaction is demonstrated by the visible finger engaging directly with the interface. By wearing a Microsoft HoloLens 2, users can interact with the digital models in the physical space, allowing them to access and explore the relevant information intuitively, which supports on-site inspection, informed renovation planning, and effective decision-making for heritage building management.

This integrated workflow, combining BIM, sensor-based monitoring, AR/VR visualization, and interactive user engagement, demonstrates a comprehensive approach for digitally supported heritage renovation. By enabling stakeholders to visualise maintenance needs, compare renovation scenarios, and interact with environmental data within immersive environments, the system significantly enhances the transparency, efficiency, and precision of decision-making in heritage building management.

(a) Maintenance information

(b) Before-and-after renovation scenarios

(c) Environment monitoring visualisation

Figure 13: User interface in AR interaction

3.1.5. Deployment

During the development process, continuous communication has been maintained with the pilot sites to ensure alignment with their specific needs and conditions. The BIM model used within the platform was directly provided by Pilot 6 (Poland), representing a heritage building within the pilot site, ensuring that the platform's data structures and functionalities align with the actual conditions of the heritage asset. Additionally, the platform's functionalities have been iteratively discussed and refined in collaboration with the pilot teams, ensuring that the developed features are practical, usable, and directly applicable to their workflows.

For the deployment phase, direct communication with Pilot 6 (Poland) has confirmed that the developed application can be applied on-site, allowing local personnel to visualise and compare different renovation plans within the actual heritage building environment. This will support informed decision-making and enhance stakeholder engagement during the renovation process. Given that the service requires the use of hardware devices for AR visualisation, Pilot 6 has been informed of the necessary equipment specifications, including the Microsoft HoloLens 2 for AR deployment and compatible computing devices to ensure seamless operation of the system.

For potential replicators, the service is designed to be scalable and adaptable to other heritage sites across Europe and globally. As long as BIM models and, where applicable, sensor data are available,

the platform can be customized to incorporate site-specific information, renovation strategies, and local regulations. For a new project, the preparation of a BIM model is required — if not already available, it typically takes around 2–4 months to develop depending on the project size. Once established, the BIM model can be directly imported into the platform. Renovation strategies can then be incorporated through corresponding functionality development within the platform, enabling site-specific customization. The modular structure of the system allows new sites to import their HBIM models and renovation plans seamlessly, enabling before-and-after scenario visualisation and on-site AR/VR deployment with minimal additional configuration. Potential replicators will be provided with guidelines on required hardware (e.g., AR headsets such as Microsoft HoloLens 2) and recommended workflows to facilitate effective integration into their renovation and maintenance activities, supporting evidence-based decision-making, stakeholder engagement, and sustainable heritage preservation in diverse contexts.

3.2. s.2 Modeling and simulation environment

3.2.1. Service overview

The main aim of the ‘Modeling and simulation environment’ service is to develop integrated renovation roadmaps for the INHERIT cultural heritage buildings, including different energy efficient measures and financing aspects. The service consists of a user interface that will facilitate the data collection from the users and their interactions with the service and from a simulation tool, the DREEM¹ model.

The primary objective of the service is to facilitate the decision-making process of the CH building owners/ users with regard to their building’s renovation, considering the energy consumption and the related costs of interventions. To achieve this, the ‘Modeling and simulation environment’ is implemented following the main steps:

- Collection of data related to building characteristics and energy consumption related data.
- Creating the dynamic energy simulation model of the building before interventions (baseline).
- Calibrating the model using the data collected for the building.
- Collecting the preferences of building interventions (a checklist of possible renovation actions has been deployed).
- Simulating the energy-efficient scenarios.
- Conducting the techno-economic assessment.
- Wrapping up the possible renovation actions with potential costs into concrete renovation roadmaps.

3.2.2. Input & output data

Input data

The primary input to this service is the building characteristics and the energy efficiency measures that would be simulated for the pilots. Thus, mainly static data will be utilised, but also dynamic data will be exploited to calibrate the baseline of the energy consumption of the buildings.

Indicative data that will be used include general information about the building as presented in the following table:

Building Characteristics	
Type of building/ usage	(e.g., church)
Year of Construction or Renovation	(e.g., 1945)
Total Floor area of the building	(e.g., 125 m ²)
Total area of external walls	(e.g., 52.5 m ²)
Total Roof area of the building:	(e.g., 125 m ²)
Windows system	
Total window area	(e.g., 24 m ²)

Table 2: Inputs regarding the general information on the building required by the “Modeling and Simulation service”

Data regarding the thermodynamic specificities of the buildings and their heating, cooling, and lighting technologies will also be collected, as presented in Table 3:

Building envelope features/ Construction features (U-values)	
U_{wall}	(e.g., 1 W/m ² /K)
U_{floor}	(e.g., 0.7 W/m ² /K)
U_{floor}	(e.g., 0.8 W/m ² /K)
U_{window}	(e.g., 2.7 W/m ² /K)
Building system	
Heating system	(e.g., Central Oil Boiler)
Nominal capacity	(e.g., 13 kW)

Cooling system	(e.g., AC Split)
Nominal capacity	(e.g., 8.9 kW)
EER (if available)	(e.g., 5)
Lighting equipment	(e.g., 46 lightbulbs)
Lighting equipment capacity	(e.g., 30 kW)

Table 3: Inputs regarding the thermodynamics and heating, cooling, and lighting technologies of the building required in the “Modeling and Simulation service”

After these data have been selected and the simulation baselines of the buildings have been created, dynamic data regarding the energy consumption of the buildings and specifically about the heating, cooling, lighting, and appliances, will be used in order to calibrate the model. Depending on the pilot building, these data can be collected through the sensors installed or through utility bills.

Finally, after the creation of the baselines and the calibration of the model, a catalogue of energy efficiency measures that would be simulated will be decided with pilots based on the energy efficiency measures identified in T3.4.

An indicative list of measures that could be tested is presented in Table 4.

Category	Retrofitting actions
Building Envelope	Insulation of external walls
	Insulation of roof
	Insulation of floor
	Double glazed windows
	Triple glazed windows
	Insulation of internal walls
HVAC	Cooling & Heating
	Water, ground and air source heat pumps
	Replacement of inefficient boilers with condensing gas boilers
	Air conditioning improvement
	Replacement of inefficient boilers with electric heaters
	Replacement of inefficient boilers with biomass boilers

Other measures	Lighting & smart actions
	Replacement of lamps with LED lamps
	Smart thermostat

Table 4: Catalogue of renovation measures that could be tested in the pilots

Output data

The main output of the service will be the building’s potential energy savings and the heating and cooling energy consumption for different renovation scenarios. Indicative examples of how the outputs would look are illustrated in Figure 14 (a-b):

(a) Total energy consumption

(b) Total daily energy consumption

Figure 14: Visualisation of the potential outputs of the ‘Modeling and simulation environment’ service

In addition to the energy related outputs, where it is feasible depending on the available data of each pilot, a techno-economic assessment will take place in order to facilitate the building owners’ and operators’ decision-making.

3.2.3. Updated architecture & technical specification

The overall architecture remains mostly identical to the one in the previous deliverable (D4.1). It consists of a user interface for data collection and the DREEM¹ simulation tool, as seen in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Visualisation of the ‘Modeling and simulation environment’ service architecture

The user interface consists of a front-end made with React (JS) and a back-end made with the Laravel framework (PHP). The front-end pages are styled with the help of the Tailwind CSS framework. The user authentication is handled by Laravel Sanctum and requires an email address and a password to log users in. The application’s data is stored in a MySQL database and the application itself is served using nginx. The backend communicates with the database through the Eloquent ORM (object-relational mapper). The application translations get automatically generated using the DeepL API and the Google Cloud Translation API, for languages that are not yet supported by DeepL.

After creating the user profile, the users are required to provide information regarding the building characteristics as presented below in Figures 16 and 17.

Figure 16: Screenshot displaying the main information of the building profile required

Figure 17: Screenshot displaying the technical characteristics of the building required

After completing the information required from the building users, we extract the inputs in a .csv file, and the development of the simulation environment proceeds.

The DREEM simulation model consists of multiple components, each of which is composed of additional modules. The overall architecture of the model, as visualised in Figure 18, makes it flexible to be adapted, modified, and extended in the future. All the modules of the model were developed using the “Buildings” library², which is an open-source, freely available Modelica library for building energy and control systems. Modelica is an equation-based, object-oriented modelling language for the simulation of dynamic systems, and has been used in several studies and applications for the design and simulation of various building energy and control systems. Alongside the Modelica models, Python scripts have been developed to model parts of the DR and control components and to enable the interface with the Dymola simulation environment.

Figure 18: The architecture of the DREEM model

3.2.4. Implementation: second technology release

During this implementation phase, our primary focus has been on collecting the necessary data to establish validated baselines for the pilot buildings. We began by reviewing the dataset compiled in D5.1 to assess completeness and identify gaps that could hinder further analysis. Following this assessment, we conducted targeted interviews with the pilot site leaders to guide them through the data entry process and to resolve any difficulties encountered with the user interface. Given the complexity of the buildings involved, acquiring detailed information, particularly regarding U-values and the specific materials used in different components of the building envelope, has proven challenging. As a result, the process of obtaining and verifying this technical data has been lengthy but essential to ensure the robustness of the baseline models.

Based on the data collected, we initiated the development of simulation baselines within the DREEM model. As illustrated in Figure 19, the model's user interface integrates several key modules that support a comprehensive representation of each pilot building. These include modules for weather data, building envelope characteristics, HVAC technologies, thermal and comfort setpoints, appliance profiles, and occupancy schedules. The modular structure enables a flexible yet detailed configuration of building parameters, which is essential for producing reliable simulation outputs tailored to each pilot case.

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Figure 19: INHERIT pilot baselines developed within the DREEM model.

In each module, we have to insert detailed inputs regarding the building characteristics and its technical specifications. The inputs catalogue for the building envelope is presented below in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Inputs required for the building envelope within the DREEM model.

3.2.5. Deployment

The service will be applied to Pilot 2 (France), Pilot 4 (Latvia), Pilot 8 (Turkey), and replicated to Pilot 7 (Sweden). The data collection process has been almost completed for Pilot 4 and Pilot 8, and the simulation of the baseline of the buildings is in progress. The data collected from Pilot 2 is currently being processed in order to frame the application in line with the current renovation of the building.

We are in discussions with Pilot 7 to identify the replication potential and apply the service in the pilot building or specific areas of the pilot building.

3.3. s.3 Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning

3.3.1. Service overview

Historic buildings have properties and qualities that must be preserved when refurbishing or reusing a building. Suitable renovation measures are, however, limited due to heritage values represented in these buildings. At the same time, a number of economic, resource, environmental and societal parameters and criteria should be taken into account in order to identify, select and implement the optimal renovation strategy for cultural historical buildings. To this end, a number of European projects and initiatives have worked towards providing decision support for selecting renovation and restoration measures in historic buildings. Nevertheless, the methods proposed tend to be only instrumental and overly simplified rather than addressing the fundamental questions of how complex multi-criteria decisions are made in current practice, and how informed decisions could be facilitated. Within the context of this project, a decision support tool for optimal renovation planning based on explicit multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) methods is developed using pertinent renovation options and analysis of these options performances given identified relevant criteria.

This decision support tool for optimal renovation planning for cultural heritage buildings will be based on outranking multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) methods. This specific group of MCDA methods is best suited for group decision aiding for energy and environmental decision problems since they decompose the problem into measurable attributes and encompass a non-compensatory criteria aggregation algorithm that supports a strong sustainability concept (Salminen et al 1998; Polatidis et al 2006). This means that a very poor performance of a possible alternative to one criterion cannot be fully compensated by a very good performance in another criterion. In that way, critical environmental and cultural values can be preserved. At the same time, the particular notion of the veto threshold used by the ELCTRE family of MCDA outranking methods can secure that constraints posed by regulations for cultural heritage buildings in all INHERIT pilots and countries would be enforced (Rogers and Bruen, 1998; Polatidis et al, 2015).

This service will allow the application of a MCDA methodological framework to improve the condition of the historical buildings through efficient decision-making for optimal renovation, considering environmental, economic, cultural heritage, and societal factors, as well as stakeholders' needs.

3.3.2. Input & output data

The service's workflow is visualised below in Figure 21.

Figure 21: s.3 - User Flow Diagram

Step 1: The user opens the service on the platform (key building details, i.e. name, building ID, building characterization, potential energy efficiency or renovation measures, etc. are imported from the relevant INHERIT databases). Examples for each INHERIT pilot building will be included.

Step 2: On the first page, the user selects potential energy efficiency/renovation measures and determines the criteria to evaluate them. Measures and criteria are taken from INHERIT Del3.1: First INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework (INHERIT Hub of Measures and INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring Pillar database). Presented measures include already included 83 alternative measures and 38 potential pillars/criteria.

Step 3: The user identifies relevant stakeholders/decision makers and inputs the elicited criteria weights for each stakeholder/decision maker. Initial criteria weights for all Assessment and Monitoring Pillars and the criteria beneath have already been elicited. This database of initial criteria evaluation weights' will be used as a first step for the integrated comparative analysis of selected measures, but the user would be able to refine/modify the criteria weights and see the difference in rankings.

Step 4: The performance of each energy efficiency/renovation measure for each criterion is input by the user. Benchmark or measured values will be provided by the relevant INHERIT databases for every Pilot, but the user would be able to change the possible values for the criteria for their case and adopt the evaluation accordingly.

Step 5: On a second page, the user goes to a results page where the performance of each energy efficiency/renovation measure for each stakeholder/decision maker is shown and ranked against other selected measures.

Step 6: The user may return to the first page to perform sensitivity analyses with the results, manually updating the various input data either by using pre-generated levels of adjustments. Changes in input data will be reflected in the second page results for each stakeholder/decision maker.

The service will be a methodological framework and tool that would guide decision-makers to: identify/select available and plausible renovation actions; develop/adopt sustainability criteria to assess these actions together with the related scales, units of measurement and ways of assessment; evaluate the performance of each action to each criterion; elicit and model the preference of stakeholders on these criteria, rank potential actions from best to worst based on individual performance and criteria weights; initiate feedback and decision loop; propose solution(s).

Input data

This tool will rely on the following data sets to establish the performance of different renovation options. The set of potential renovation options will be selectable by users from the INHERIT Hub of Measures, while the criteria used to evaluate these options will be selected by users from the INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring Pillar database. The service user will be prompted to provide their preference thresholds on each criterion, or the values at which the user begins to perceive differences between two alternatives being compared for a criterion (indifference threshold) and when the user perceives the differences between two alternatives to be sufficiently large that one alternative is strongly preferred (preference threshold). A similar procedure will be used to determine the veto threshold, depending on the specific MCDA method used and if needed. As a final step, the user may select the INHERIT AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process) pre-defined criteria weights for all Assessment and Monitoring Pillars (T3.2: INHERIT assessment and monitoring framework) or provide weights, using a 100-point system, to each of the criterion used to evaluate the renovation options to indicate each's relative importance in the evaluation (Saaty, 1980; Vaidya and Kumar, 2006; Hajkowicz et al 2000). The user may enter several different weights representing the viewpoints of different stakeholders at this stage.

The following datasets are expected to be relevant for most or all renovation options.

Dataset	Description
Energy balance sheet for heating: input – output analysis	Heat demand: type and amount of energy used to cover heat demand
Energy balance sheet for cooling: input – output analysis	Cooling demand: type and amount of energy used to cover cooling demand

Energy balance sheet for electrical appliances: input – output analysis	Electrical appliances demand: amount of energy used to cover electrical appliances demand
Energy balance sheet for hot water demand: input – output analysis	Hot water demand: type and amount of energy used to cover hot water demand

Table 5: Datasets for renovation options

List of items: Heat demand assessment; cooling demand assessment; electrical appliances demand assessment; hot water demand assessment; potential renovation measures will be identified together with their environmental impact and implementation cost; data base of wider societal actors' (users, stakeholders, decision-makers, shadow players, ...), specific preferences will be established via interviews, surveys, focus groups, etc. A simple example of the user input data start page could look like is presented in Figure 22 below.

CASE-STUDY Example: CH renovation project selection problem		Please define here your Scenario, Criteria, Preference Thresholds, Decision Makers and their Weights!			
Scenario		Criteria			
		Energy Technology	Investment	Impact on users' comfort	Economic Cost
		Units	Investment	Qualitative 1-10	Cost
		Decision	€	€	€
1	Scenario 1: Replacement of windows	2 300	230,00	8,00	30000
2	Scenario 2: Ceiling insulation	4 100	400,00	5,00	6700
3	Scenario 3: Installation of heat pumps	7 000	670,00	7,00	50000
4	Scenario 4: Crack sealing	1 200	140,00	3,00	5000
		Preference Threshold			
		1 450,00	132,50	1,25	11 250,00
		Decision Makers - DMs			
		Weights			
	DM 1: Property manager	20	20	20	100
	DM 2: Property user	10	10	10	100
	DM 3: Building owner	10	5	20	40
	DM 4: Regulatory agency	20	20	20	100
		SUM			
		Preference Note: Sum of weights should be 100			

Figure 22: User data input page visualisation example

Output data

Depending on the method chosen by the service user, different outputs are possible from the service. These outputs include a ranking, selection or categorization of the selected renovation options. A brief description of these outputs is provided below.

Ranking - Using the users' inputs, the different renovation options are ranked from the most preferred option to the least preferred option.

Selection - Using the users' inputs, the most suitable alternative from the given renovation options is identified.

Categorization - Using the users' inputs, the given renovation options are categorized.

Sensitivity analysis - The service user will be able to perform sensitivity analyses on the results of the MCDA using three different methods. The user will be able to evaluate how changes in the renovation options'

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performances in a single or across several of the given criteria impact the results. Further, the service user may adjust the *thresholds* provided as well as the *weights* provided to evaluate any changes in the provided results. These adjustments may be made manually by the user or by selecting pre-generated levels of adjustments, i.e., 10% adjustments to criterion performances, thresholds based on calculated average values, or standardized weight allocations.

Figure 23: Decision-maker 1's scenario rankings.

Figure 24: Decision-maker 2's scenario rankings.

Figure 25: Decision-maker 3's scenario rankings.

Figure 26: Decision-maker 4's scenario rankings.

3.3.3. Updated architecture & technical specification

This service will be deployed using the architecture in Figure 27.

Figure 27: Service 3 architecture & technical specifications

3.3.4. Deployment

The INHERIT Multi-Criteria Decision Support tool is currently being implemented at the INHERIT Pilot 7, Visby, Sweden. First results are expected during Autumn 2025. Lessons learned and good practices will be implemented in the MCDA tool design and included in subsequent applications to the remaining INHERIT pilots will follow.

4. ‘Monitoring, operation & management’ services

4.1. s.4 Indoor environmental quality & thermal comfort optimization

4.1.1. Service overview

The service is implemented as a web-based application that enables real-time visualisation of IEQ conditions across different areas of CH buildings. It integrates sensor data to continuously monitor key IEQ parameters—such as thermal conditions, air quality, acoustic and visual comfort—and detects anomalies or irregular patterns that may indicate suboptimal practices or deteriorating well-being.

The service also supports user feedback collection, allowing building occupants and facility managers to report perceived discomfort or issues, which are then combined with sensor data for a more holistic understanding. Based on this input, the service uses advanced analytics and data-driven models to provide actionable recommendations—both structural and behavioural—that aim to improve occupant well-being within the bounds of the preservation requirements of historic building.

Following the structure of the frontend of the service, its workflow is summarized as follows:

- **Home**
The user accesses the service, getting an overview of the building and its current IEQ status. The overview includes key building details, the list of rooms being monitored, and a report of IEQ-related KPIs, assessing the current level of IEQ metrics, across all rooms.
- **Live View**
By clicking on a certain room, the user is transferred to the “Live View” tab, where they observe the respective IEQ KPIs using real-time data. In the graphs provided, the user can inspect potential anomalies and provide feedback about their comfortability.
- **Patterns**
In the second tab, the user finds graphs that summarize past performance of IEQ variables, aggregated by weekday, week, or month. Algorithms can also be used to automatically detect anomalies and assist pattern identification, thereby supporting the prioritization of corrective measures.
- **Insights and Proposals**
In this tab, users gain deeper insights into the consistency of IEQ conditions — specifically, how often measured values remain within defined acceptable bounds. An algorithm is used to automatically identify problematic hours, days, or months. Finally, actions are proposed based on the severity of inconsistencies to promote a healthier indoor environment, inspired by the INHERIT “Hub of Measures” – part of the INHERIT D3.1: First INHERIT

Assessment & Monitoring Framework – a list of measures developed in cooperation with pilots that have potential to improve environmental conditions and are practically viable.

The service will be applied to pilot sites in Greece (Pilot 3) and Latvia (Pilot 4) and will be replicated in Croatia (Pilot 1).

4.1.2. Input & output data

The primary input to the IEQ optimization service is sensor-based environmental measurement data, typically collected at hourly intervals from different areas within each pilot building. The system captures multiple IEQ-related variables, including:

- Temperature
- Humidity
- CO₂ concentration
- Noise levels
- Illuminance

Each metric is recorded through a virtual sensor, which represents a single measurement channel (e.g., temperature or humidity) on a physical sensor device using the relational database of s.O. A single physical sensor may therefore expose multiple virtual sensors depending on the number of parameters it measures.

A critical aspect of the data model is sensor mapping. Virtual sensors are associated with physical sensors via their unique MAC addresses. Physical sensors are, in turn, assigned to specific rooms, and rooms are mapped to their corresponding pilot sites (i.e., the buildings or campuses being monitored). This hierarchy, visualised below, ensures full traceability of every data point, from measurement back to physical location and context.

Measurements

↳ Virtual Sensors

↳ Sensors (physical)

↳ Rooms

↳ Pilots (Buildings/Campuses)

In addition to dynamic, real-time measurement data, the system also relies on static data that defines the structure, relationships, and metadata necessary for interpreting measurements. Moreover, user-generated data is produced as users utilize the application.

Static Data	Dynamic Data	User Generated Data
Sensors, Rooms, Proposals, Units & Metrics, Bounds	Measurements (timestamped values), Virtual sensors	Feedback

Table 6: Data used for s.4

In addition to measurement data, several supporting tables define key relationships and metadata: Metric definitions and units are stored in dedicated tables (metrics, units), acceptable value ranges for each metric are defined per room and per season in a separate bounds table, user feedback on environmental comfort is captured and stored independently, proposals for improving IEQ are maintained in a flexible format and can be linked to multiple metrics. Table 6 summarizes the key database tables and their relationships.

Data Type	Description
Measurements	Timestamped values recorded by virtual sensors.
Virtual Sensors	Represent a measurable parameter linked to a metric and unit.
Sensors	Physical device identified by MAC address, deployed in a specific room.
Rooms	Spatial unit of a building, associated with a pilot and contains sensors.
Pilots	Represents the building or building complex under study.
Metrics & Units	Two small tables that define measurable metrics and associated units.
Bounds	Defines acceptable thresholds for metrics per room and season.
Proposals	Recommendations for improving IEQ, potentially linked to multiple metrics.
Feedback	Collected user feedback on environmental comfort and perception. The feedback is structured as columns named as monitored metrics, and the response is in integer form: 0 - feeling fine, 1 – feeling hot, -1 – feeling cold.

Table 7: Type and description of data used by s.4.

The structure of the IEQ data is organized in a relational PostgreSQL database, is presented in Figure 28:

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Figure 28: Tables utilized by s.4.

4.1.3. Updated architecture & technical specification

The overall architecture of the service has remained mostly identical to the one described in D4.1, with a few adjustments. Figure 29 presents the updated service architecture, summarizing the technologies utilized.

Figure 29: Architecture over of service 4.

The service is structured into three core layers—Presentation, Application, and Database—to ensure modularity, scalability, and maintainability. The integration between the Application and Database Layers is managed using Docker, which provides containerized environments for streamlined development, deployment, and scalability.

- **Database Layer**

All data is stored and managed using PostgreSQL, a robust open-source relational database. The architecture differentiates between static data, dynamic data, and generated data, as described in the previous section.

- **Application Layer (Backend)**

Implemented in Python, this layer acts as the backbone of the system. It is responsible for handling database communication, performing data analysis, extracting insights, and running detection algorithms. The Application Layer orchestrates backend logic and interacts with both the frontend and the database through a centralized REST API.

- **Presentation Layer (Frontend)**

This layer handles user interaction through a frontend built with React and TypeScript. It supports features such as user authorization, data visualisation, and parameter configuration. The frontend

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communicates with the backend through a REST API, enabling real-time data-driven UI updates and report generation.

4.1.4. Implementation: second technology release

This section focuses on the Application and Presentation layers, as described previously. The service is built with modular and scalable architecture, ensuring ease of maintenance and extensibility. Moreover, it is deployed on a host machine, with deployment and testing workflows fully automated through GitLab CI/CD pipelines. These pipelines enable the entire development team to continuously integrate changes and immediately test updates across both backend and frontend components. The following subsections outline the structure and technologies used in each layer.

4.1.4.1. Backend implementation

To illustrate the backend implementation, it's useful to present the folder structure of the backend project. A structured view is presented in Table 8:

— Dockerfile	# Container configuration for backend deployment
— requirements.txt	# Python dependencies list
— backend	
— database.py	# Database connection and session management
— main.py	# Entry point for starting the FastAPI application
— common	# Reusable utilities and shared logic
— bounds.py	# Helper functions for value bounds and limits
— user_id.py	# User ID management or parsing logic
— utility.py	# General-purpose helper functions
— crud	# Database interaction logic (Create, Read, Update, Delete)
— data.py	# CRUD operations for core data
— desc.py	# CRUD for description-related data
— generated.py	# CRUD for generated/processed data
— files	
— proposals_file.csv	# Input dataset for proposal generation
— functions	# Core backend processing and domain logic
— auth.py	# User authentication logic
— detection_functions.py	# Detection algorithms implementation
— insights.py	# Data insights extraction logic
— lifeview_graphs.py	# Logic for real-time visual analytics
— patterns_graphs.py	# Graphs and analysis of recurring patterns

proposal_functions.py	# Logic for generating user proposals
models	# Pydantic and ORM models
data.py	# Data models for primary datasets
desc.py	# Models for descriptive metadata
generated.py	# Models for generated content
routes	# API endpoints grouped by feature
common.py	# Shared or utility endpoints
home_rooms.py	# Endpoints for home page and room summaries
room_liveview.py	# Real-time room data visualisation endpoints
room_patterns.py	# Routes for detecting and showing patterns
room_proposals.py	# Routes for proposal generation and retrieval

Table 8: Back-end implementation of s.4

The backend architecture is implemented in Python using FastAPI for RESTful services and SQLAlchemy for database interactions. It is designed in a modular way to clearly separate concerns, ensure testability, and facilitate further development. All endpoints, routes and functions presented above can be organized based on their functionality as follows:

- **Database Communication**

Handled primarily via the crud/ and models/ directories, these modules utilize SQLAlchemy ORM to perform create, read, update, and delete operations across different database tables. Specifically, crud/ contains logic to interact with static, dynamic, and generated data and models/ defines Pydantic and SQLAlchemy models for data validation and schema control.

- **Data Analysis**

The main data processing logic is defined in the functions/ folder and consumed by various endpoints in the routes/ folder. These are critical for transforming raw sensor data into insights. These routes and their connected functions are organized by the respective page in frontend and can be summarized as follows:

- **Home** (*home_rooms.py* route) – for each room an endpoint returns its characteristics and current IEQ situation.
- **Live View** (*room_liveview.py* route + *liveview_graphs.py* function) – latest records of multiple or single sensors (selected by user) are averaged and compared to their optimal bounds. All records of the present day are organized on hourly basis and presented as graph with visualised bounds.
- **Patterns** (*room_patterns.py* route + *patterns_graphs* function) – historical records of multiple or single sensors (selected by user) are aggregated by day, weekday, week,

month or season. There are two graph functions – average hourly line plot and summarized bar plot.

- **Insights** (*room_proposals* route) – although this page is mostly covered in a following section, some non-proposal data visualisation is necessary and a specific endpoint presents average values for a selected time window, as well as their consistency.

- **Insights Extraction**

The process of extracting actionable insights is handled through the endpoint in *routes/room_proposals.py* and heavily relies on logic implemented in *functions/proposal_functions.py*. This module is composed of three key functions:

- **Consistency calculation** – Determines how often IEQ metrics stay within or deviate from optimal thresholds. It is covered by the endpoint that belongs to the Data Analysis section.
- **Problematic period detection** – Identifies specific months, days, and hours where comfort conditions degrade. Measurements are filtered for occupancy hours and evaluated using dynamic thresholds (seasonal, spatial). Each measurement is classified into:
 - Acceptable (p_0): within defined bounds
 - Mild deviation (p_1): slightly outside bounds (within tolerance)
 - Severe deviation (p_2): beyond tolerance

Using this classification, a penalty score is calculated:

$$\text{Penalty Score} = \frac{0 * p_0 + 1 * p_1 + 2 * p_2}{p_0 + p_1 + p_2}$$

This score is computed over months, then broken down to days and hours to localize problematic periods. Any score > 0.5 flags that time segment as suboptimal.

- **Proposal matching** – Uses predefined proposals from *proposals_file.csv* to recommend targeted actions, ranked by severity and affected metrics. These proposals were developed within T3.4 “INHERIT Hub of measures inventory for efficient, inclusive, resilient and low-emission CH”. Based on the score, the system maps the results to interventions:
 - >95% compliant → No measure needed
 - 60–95% → Behavioural adjustments needed
 - 20–60% → Soft measures (e.g. ventilation tuning) needed
 - <20% → Structural renovations needed

If a parameter is missing due to sensor absence, the system suggests installing a sensor to enable future assessment.

The modules above compile the insights mechanism that follows a penalty-based scoring system which evaluates environmental parameters (temperature, humidity, CO₂, light, noise) against acceptable comfort ranges defined in EN 16798-1:2019¹.

- **Detection Functions**

This module provides tools for time-based anomaly detection and classification of working vs. non-working hours in time series data. Key functionalities include:

- **Anomaly Detection** - This function identifies anomalies, values significantly higher or lower than expected, in a dataset using the IQR method, calculated as the difference between the top 5% and bottom 5% percentiles of the data. A threshold is then defined as 1.5 times the IQR, and any values lying outside the calculated lower and upper bounds are flagged as anomalies.
- **Working Hours Detection** - This function generates an hourly timestamp range between two dates and labels each timestamp as a working hour (wh = 1) or non-working hour (wh = 0). Non-working hours during weekdays are stated by pilots, while other non-working hours include weekends and public holidays. In case of irregular working hours and availability of energy consumption data, an algorithm that identifies specific working hours based on energy consumption can be used instead.

4.1.4.2. Frontend implementation

The frontend is implemented using React with TypeScript, offering a responsive, interactive interface for users to explore environmental data, configure parameters, and view recommendations. This design follows a modular component-based architecture, enabling scalability and reusability across different views and contexts, as structured Table 9:

—— Dockerfile	# Defines the container image for frontend deployment
—— package.json	# Lists project dependencies and scripts for React app
—— README.md	# Project overview and usage instructions
—— node_modules	# Automatically installed packages (ignored in version control)
—— public	# Static files (index.html, favicon, etc.)
—— src	# Main application source code
—— App.tsx	# Root React component
—— App.css	# Styles for the root component

¹ https://standards.iteh.ai/catalog/standards/cen/b4f68755-2204-4796-854a-56643dfcfe89/en-16798-1-2019?srsId=AfmBOoqXAQsPuqiLRKeFjxk4xf_4n9Ntg3V80b7cgB1hfQeeuy1QQh

—	App.test.tsx	# Sample test for root component
—	index.tsx	# Entry point: renders App into DOM
—	index.css	# Global styles
—	axiosInstance.ts	# Pre-configured Axios instance for API communication
—	Keycloak.ts	# Keycloak authentication setup
—	pilotContext.tsx	# React context for managing selected pilot/site
—	react-app-env.d.ts	# Type declarations for the React environment
—	reportWebVitals.ts	# Performance measurement utilities
—	setupTests.ts	# Test environment configuration
—	Common	# Utility files and shared types
—	Enums.ts	# Enumerations used across the app
—	Helpers.ts	# General utility functions
—	pilotInfo.ts	# Static data or logic about pilot sites
—	Types.ts	# Shared TypeScript interfaces and types
—	components	# Reusable UI components
—	BigSwitch.tsx	# Toggle for enabling/disabling features
—	InsightsGauges.tsx	# Circular gauges for insights visualisation
—	MetricsDropDownSelect.tsx	# Dropdown to select IEQ metrics
—	Nav.tsx	# Top navigation bar
—	PilotDropDown.tsx	# Dropdown for selecting pilot site
—	PilotSelector.tsx	# Pilot selection logic
—	ServiceSwitch.tsx	# Switch control for optional service views
—	StatGauges.tsx	# Displays summarized status values
—	useKeycloakAuthentication.tsx	# Custom hook to handle login/auth state
—	ScaleLines	# Visual scale line indicators for IEQ metrics
—	ScaleLine.tsx	# Base component for scale lines
—	ScaleLine.css	# Styles for scale lines
—	AirQualityScaleLine.tsx	
—	TemperatureScaleLine.tsx	
—	HumidityScaleLine.tsx	
—	VisualComfortScaleLine.tsx	
—	AcousticComfortScaleLine.tsx	
—	PercentageScaleLine.tsx	
—	pages	# Main view pages (routes in the app)
—	Securedpage.tsx	# Wrapper for routes requiring authentication
—	BuildingOverview	# High-level building status overview
—	BuildingOverview.tsx	# Displays all rooms and overall metrics

RoomPage	# Single-room detailed view with multiple tabs
FeedbackModal.tsx	# Modal to collect user comfort feedback
InsightsTab.tsx	# Insights section (uses proposal recommendations)
LiveViewTab.tsx	# Real-time sensor readings and gauges
PatternsTab.tsx	# Visualises historical trends
RoomPage.css	# Styles for Room page layout
RoomPage.tsx	# Container for all room-specific tabs

Table 9: Front-end implementation of s.4

The pages are best described in detail with use of screenshots.

- **Home**

The home page provides an overview of IEQ metrics across all rooms within the building. Each room is assessed and visually represented using color-coded indicators, allowing users to quickly identify areas that require attention. These visual cues are based on thresholds that are either aligned with international standards or customized according to the specific characteristics and preservation needs of the building, see Figure 30.

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Figure 30: Screenshot of s.4 “Home” page.

- **Live View**

The Live View page offers real-time monitoring and evaluation of IEQ parameters within a selected room. Users can observe up-to-date readings for metrics such as temperature, humidity, air quality, noise, and lighting, see Figure 31. Additionally, the interface allows users to provide direct feedback on their comfort levels, which can be used to refine future assessments and personalize recommendations, see Figure 32.

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Figure 31: Screenshot of s.4 “Live View” page.

Figure 32: Screenshot of s.4 “Live View” page with active feedback window.

- **Patterns**

The Patterns page presents a historical analysis of IEQ variables, allowing users to explore trends aggregated by weekday, week, or month. The system automatically detects anomalies and highlights irregular behaviours, helping users identify recurring issues or patterns of deviation. This analytical view supports data-driven prioritization of corrective actions by revealing when and where environmental conditions most frequently fall outside acceptable ranges, see Figure 33.

Figure 33: Screenshot of s.4 “Patterns” page.

- **Insights:**

The Insights page evaluates how consistently each IEQ parameter remains within its defined comfort bounds over a selected period. It automatically detects problematic hours, days, and months where deviations are most frequent or severe. Based on the severity and frequency of these inconsistencies, the system recommends targeted actions to improve indoor conditions, see Figure 34. These proposals are drawn from the INHERIT “Hub of Measures” – a list of measures, developed in cooperation with pilots as part of INHERIT D3.1 “First INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework”, ensuring that suggested interventions are both effective and appropriate for cultural heritage environments.

Figure 34: Screenshot of s.4 “Insights” page.

4.1.5. Deployment

The sensors required for developing the service have been installed in the pilot buildings and connected to the data exchange platform developed within s.0. From the 4 pilots that participate in the service, 3 pilots have stable data flow, 1 pilot’s sensors have stopped sending data due to technical issues, and the reason is under investigation.

Through a message broker, data is continuously fed into the database, enabling the execution of all previously described functions. Anomalies from sensor failures or aberrant values are flagged through an anomaly detection algorithm, while a dedicated sensor health monitoring module is

under development. The application is currently hosted under two domains: the *epu.ntua.gr* is for testing and development, while a stable version is under the *SingularLogic* domain. Both versions are secured with Keycloak-based authentication. Pilot users will be registered using their email addresses, alongside the development team.

4.2. s.5 Energy forecasting & intelligent management

4.2.1. Service overview

This service focuses on enhancing the efficiency and intelligence of energy usage of CH buildings by combining real-time data visualisation, advanced analytics, and machine learning techniques. A web application enables real-time visualisation of different types of energy consumption. Benchmark comparison and pattern visualisation help users identify periods with issues and overconsumption. Energy forecasts are produced using a machine learning model, trained on each pilot's data.

Overall, the service enables users to visualise and analyse electricity consumption patterns, offering clear insights into energy-intensive activities or periods across different areas of the building. It supports the identification of irregular or excessive usage that may compromise both operational efficiency and preservation efforts. Following the structure of the frontend of the service, its workflow is organized as:

- **Home**

The user accesses the service, getting an overview of the building's energy end uses (e.g. total, HVAC, devices). The overview includes key building details, the list of uses that are being monitored, and a report of energy consumption since the start of the year, as well as the total accumulated energy cost and produced CO₂.

- **Live View**

By clicking on a certain energy end use, the user is transferred to the "Live View" tab, where they observe the specific energy consumption using real-time data and analyse it. In the graph provided, the user can inspect hourly energy consumption during the day, and benchmarking bar plot provides visualised comparison of hourly energy consumption with the day, week or month before, as well as an easily understood explanation of the bar plot. The choice of data representation methods was guided by the widely accepted, intuitive formats commonly used in similar applications.

- **Patterns**

In the second tab, the user finds graphs that summarize past performance of specific energy consumption type, aggregated by weekday, week, or month. It also automatically detects anomalies and assists pattern identification. By changing the time interval under investigation, the graphs dynamically change.

- **Forecasts**

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In the third tab, users can observe the energy forecasts produced for the current and following day as well as week, serving as a base for the optimizations, along with providing a visualisation of energy consumption that day.

- **Proposals**

This tab, that is still under development, will focus on recommending load shifting actions, aiming to enhance energy efficiency based on typical prices and estimated peaks. The expected improvements will also be reported.

The service will be applied to pilot sites in Croatia (Pilot 1) and Sweden (Pilot 7) and will be replicated in Greece (Pilot 3).

4.2.2. Input & output data

The primary input to the service is energy consumption data, typically collected at hourly intervals from different sensors within each pilot building. The data is captured in two formats: active energy and reactive energy, but based on sensor connections, we can determine several energy consumption types:

- Total energy consumption
- HVAC energy consumption
- Device energy consumptions

Active and reactive energy are recorded separately via a virtual sensor, similar to s.4. However, in the case of energy consumption, the physical sensor's location is of secondary importance, as switchboards may be in a different spot than the sources of energy consumption they monitor. Therefore, in coordination with pilots, during the energy consumption type mapping, each physical sensor was assigned to a specific end use. This information is saved in the metrics table. The physical sensors' only meaningful connection to the rooms is that the rooms are connected to the pilots.

In addition to real-time energy consumption data, the system also relies on static data that defines the structure, relationships, and metadata necessary for interpreting measurements. Dynamic data is served by s.0, the core data ingestion service responsible for real-time acquisition from deployed sensors. Generated data is produced by the machine learning model for more efficient value fetching.

Static Data	Dynamic Data	Model Generated Data
Sensors, Energy Types, Units	Measurements (timestamped values), Virtual sensors	Energy Forecast, Pilot Models

Table 10: Key database table

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Table 10 summarizes the key database tables and their relationships.

Data Type	Description
Measurements	Timestamped energy consumption values recorded by virtual sensors.
Virtual Sensors	Represents a measurable parameter linked to energy type and sensor.
Sensors & Rooms	Physical device identified by MAC address, linked via Rooms to specific pilot.
Pilots	Represents the building or building complex under study.
Metrics & Units	Two small tables that define measurable energy types and associated units.
Forecasts	Forecasts, produced by ML model for a specific physical sensor and timestamp are saved in database using scheduler. Run timestamp is also collected.
Pilot Models	ML models are trained weekly, and their trained state is saved to be used to produce daily forecasts.

Table 11: Type and description of data used by s.5.

The structure of the IEQ data is organized in a relational PostgreSQL database, as presented in Figure 35:

Figure 35: Tables utilized by s.5.

4.2.3. Updated architecture & technical specification

The overall architecture has remained mostly identical to the one described in D4.1, with a few adjustments. Similar to s.4, the service relies on REST API to manage core functionalities in the Application Layer, such as data analysis and ML forecasting. The scripts are executed in Python. PostgreSQL is used for data storage in the Database Layer, discussed in the previous section. Data visualisation, reports, and analytical representations are performed in the front-end using React in the Presentation Layer. The connection between the Application Layer and the Presentation Layer adopts Docker as the core containerization technology. Figure 36 presents a detailed overview of the updated service architecture, including the technologies utilized.

Figure 36: Architecture overview of s.5.

4.2.4. Implementation: second technology release

This section outlines the Application and Presentation layers of the service, focusing on the technical implementation of both backend and frontend components. The architecture remains modular and scalable and Gitlab CI/CD pipelines support automated deployment and testing. The subsections below describe the structure and technologies used for the second release of the energy forecasting and intelligent management service.

4.2.4.1. Backend implementation

To illustrate the backend implementation, the folder structure of the backend project is presented in Table 12.

— Dockerfile	# Container configuration for backend deployment
— requirements.txt	# Python dependencies list
— backend	
— database.py	# Database connection and session management
└─ main.py	# Entry point for starting the FastAPI application
— common	# Reusable utilities and shared logic
└─ utility.py	# General-purpose helper functions
— crud	# Database interaction logic (Create, Read, Update, Delete)
— data.py	# CRUD operations for core data
— desc.py	# CRUD for description-related data
└─ generated.py	# CRUD for generated/processed data
— functions	# Core backend processing and domain logic
— auth.py	# User authentication logic
— detection_functions.py	# Detection algorithms implementation
— home_page.py	# Logic for year-to-date computations of home page
— patterns_graphs.py	# Graphs and analysis of recurring patterns
└─ forecasting_functions.py	# ML model (preprocessing, tuning, training & prediction)
— models	# Pydantic and ORM models
— data.py	# Data models for primary datasets
— desc.py	# Models for descriptive metadata
└─ generated.py	# Models for generated content
— routes	# API endpoints grouped by feature
— common.py	# Shared or utility endpoints
— homepage.py	# Endpoints for home page year-to-date computations
— energy_use_live_view.py	# Routes for real-time energy monitoring and benchmarking
— energy_patterns.py	# Routes for detecting and showing patterns
└─ energy_forecasting.py	# Endpoints for forecast retrieval
— schedulers	# Automated ML forecast lifestyle
— hyparameter_sceduler.py	# Quartely Optuna hyparameter tuning for ML
models	
— model_training_sceduler.py	# Weekly training of forecast models
└─ forecasts_production_sceduler.py	# Daily execution of 7-day ahead forecasts

Table 12: s.5 back-end implementation

Like s.4, the backend is developed in Python using FastAPI for exposing RESTful APIs and SQLAlchemy to manage database operations. Its structure follows a modular design pattern to promote code clarity, testability and ease of extension.

The various endpoints and functionalities are grouped on their role:

- **Database Communication**

The core database interaction is managed through the `crud/` and `models/` directories. These components leverage SQLAlchemy ORM to execute CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations across various database entities. More specifically, `crud/` handles the logic to interact with static, dynamic, and generated data, while `models/` defines the data schemas and validation rules using both SQLAlchemy and Pydantic.

- **Data Analysis**

Raw energy measurements are transformed into usable hourly consumption data primarily through utilities in `crud/data.py`, which convert cumulative readings. These cleaned data points are further processed by scripts in the `functions/` directory, enabling accurate and consistent input for forecasting and analytical tasks.

- **Home** (*homepage.py* route) – For each pilot and energy use (e.g. total, HVAC, devices), the route computes the year-to-date energy consumption in kWh, the corresponding CO₂ emissions, and the estimated energy cost. The CO₂ emissions are calculated using average carbon intensity multipliers for 2024 provided by [ENTSO-E](#), while the energy cost is estimated based on average €/kWh values sourced from [EU annual reports](#).
- **Live View** (*energy_use_live_view.py* route + *data.py* crud) – Current-day energy measurements are computed on an hourly basis and compared against historical baselines. Absolute and percentage differences are calculated with reference to yesterday, the same weekday last week, and the same weekday over the past four weeks.
- **Patterns** (*energy_patterns.py* route + *patterns_graphs.py* function) – Records of multiple or single sensors (selected by user) are aggregated by day, weekday, week, month or season. There are two graph functions – average hourly line plot and summarized bar plot
- **Insights** – This module is currently under development and is intended to generate actionable suggestions for optimizing energy usage based on consumption trends, anomalies, and system behaviour, primarily through load shifting scenarios.

- **ML Forecasting**

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The forecasting mechanism follows a structured pipeline designed for efficiency, automation, and adaptability across pilots. It begins with the retrieval of cumulative energy data from the database, which is then transformed into hourly consumption values through feature engineering. During this stage, missing values are handled, outliers are treated, and temporal features (e.g., lags, seasonality, holidays) are generated to enhance model performance. As part of this process, missing values and outliers are handled using standard aggregation and averaging methods implemented in our database queries, ensuring robust hourly and sensor-level measurements for analysis.

Model optimization is performed quarterly using Optuna for hyperparameter tuning, followed by weekly re-training of LightGBM models tailored to each pilot's sensors. The resulting models are serialized and stored in the database.

Once trained, these models are used to generate 7-day-ahead hourly forecasts daily. The forecast outputs are stored and served through the RESTful API, which provides energy predictions filtered by sensor or energy use type. The entire workflow is orchestrated using background schedulers (APScheduler-based schedulers.), ensuring continuous operation with minimal manual intervention, see Figure 37.

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Figure 37: Forecast pipeline utilized in s.5.

- **Detection & Optimization Algorithms**

Building on the foundation created in s.4, the current implementation continues to make use of time-based detection utilities to ensure the reliability of energy data and to identify operational patterns. These functionalities remain integrated within functions/*detection_functions.py*.

- **Anomaly Detection** also applies the IQR method, dynamically calculating thresholds based on statistical percentiles to identify consumption values that significantly deviate from typical behaviour.
- **Working Hours Classification** also follows the logic introduced earlier, combining pilot-specific schedules with dynamic labelling of hourly timestamps. Where predefined working hours are not available or inconsistent, a data-driven algorithm is used to infer working periods directly from historical energy consumption.

4.2.4.2. Frontend implementation

The frontend architecture remains identical to the one described in s.4, leveraging a React-based, containerized application deployed via Docker. The implementation continues to support modular feature separation, improved component reusability, and state management through React Context API.

— Dockerfile	# Defines the container image for frontend deployment
— package.json	# Lists project dependencies and scripts for React app
— README.md	# Project overview and usage instructions
— node_modules	# Automatically installed packages (ignored in version control)
— public	# Static files (index.html, favicon, etc.)
— src	# Main application source code
— App.tsx	# Root React component
— App.css	# Styles for the root component
— App.test.tsx	# Sample test for root component
— index.tsx	# Entry point: renders App into DOM
— index.css	# Global styles
— axiosInstance.ts	# Pre-configured Axios instance for API communication
— Keycloak.ts	# Keycloak authentication setup
— pilotContext.tsx	# React context for managing selected pilot/site
— react-app-env.d.ts	# Type declarations for the React environment
— reportWebVitals.ts	# Performance measurement utilities
— setupTests.ts	# Test environment configuration

The pages are best described below using some screenshots:

- **Home**

The Home page provides a summarized visualisation of key energy indicators per energy use that is recorded in the examined pilot. The layout displays

- Energy Consumption (kWh): The year-to-date total energy consumed.
- CO₂ Emissions (kg): Estimated emissions are calculated using country-specific average carbon intensity multipliers.
- Energy Cost (€): Estimated cost computed from average kWh prices from EU annual reports.

By selecting the desired tile, the user can access additional information on patterns, forecasts, and proposals related to the selected type of energy use, see Figure 38.

Figure 38: Screenshot of s.5 “Home” page.

- **Live View**

The Live View page provides real-time monitoring of energy consumption, displayed by energy use type and sensor through a line chart. Additionally, a bar chart compares today's hourly consumption against the same sensor's consumption from the previous day, the same day last week, and the same weekday over the past four weeks, see Figure 39.

Figure 39: Screenshot of s.5 “Live View” page.

- **Patterns**

The Patterns page provides a historical overview of energy consumption, enabling users to explore trends aggregated by weekday, week, month, or season. The system automatically detects anomalies and highlights irregular patterns to help identify recurring issues. A multi-line graph visualises hourly values across selected time windows, while a bar chart displays corresponding

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averages. Users can filter results by sensor, time range, and choose whether to include or exclude non-working hours and detected anomalies, see Figure 40.

Figure 40: Screenshot of s.5 “Patterns” page.

- **Forecast**

The Forecast tab displays the output of a machine learning model trained weekly on each pilot’s sensors’ energy consumption data. The main graph presents both actual recorded consumption and predicted values. Users can select specific sensors and choose from three forecasting windows: end of day, next day, or end of week, see Figure 41.

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Figure 41: Screenshot of s.5 “Forecast” page.

- **Proposals**

This tab is currently under development. It will focus on load shifting, managing energy based on environmental quality and comfort, peak shaving or CO₂ emissions reduction, depending on the needs of each pilot.

4.2.5. Deployment

The sensors required for deploying the service have been installed in the pilot buildings’ energy control panels and connected to the data exchange platform developed within s.0. Through a message broker, data is continuously fed into the database, enabling the execution of all previously described functions. Of the 4 pilots participating in this service, 3 pilots have stable data flow but 1 pilot’s sensors have stopped sending data due to technical reasons, the issue is under investigation.

Similar to s.4, the application is currently hosted under the *epu.ntua.gr* domain, secured with Keycloak-based authentication. Pilot users will be registered using their email addresses, alongside the development team.

4.3. s.6 Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real time monitoring and management

4.3.1. Service overview

The digital twin (DT) to be developed in INHERIT is a virtual replica of a cultural heritage building designed to enhance its operation and management, particularly in terms of energy performance and indoor environmental quality. It provides valuable insights to building users and maintenance managers, supporting informed decision-making for conservation and efficiency.

The digital twin integrates a broad range of elements, combining static data from BIM models (capturing the building's architectural, structural and system details) with dynamic data from real-time monitoring systems. Advanced data processing transforms this information into performance indicators and scores, offering a comprehensive assessment of both building conditions and user interactions. Additionally, energy performance models enable scenario simulations and "what-if" analyses, allowing stakeholders to evaluate the impact of potential energy conservation measures before implementation.

The DT system will enable:

1. Remote inspection and visualisation of BIM models as well as real-time and historical data on energy and indoor environment quality.
2. Energy efficiency and indoor environment quality evaluation and monitoring.
3. Generation and visualisation of energy & IEQ performance deviation alarms.
4. Automatic sensors incident detection.
5. Identify areas for improvement and quantify savings potential based on an optimally operated and maintained reference CH.
6. Enable simulation scenarios and what-if analysis to evaluate the impact of behavioural changes or conservation measures with high accuracy.
7. Promote preventive conservation through predictive analysis of the risk of surface condensation.
8. Visualise all data and calculations in the DT graphical interface, which is divided into a 3D visualisation (BIM-based) and a navigation/control panel.

4.3.2. Input & output data

Input data

The digital twin developed at INHERIT offers the following inputs:

1- Static CH data. The DT enables to visualise all the static data included in the BIM model of the CH. The information will be collected through the BIM model file (it can be an ifc file, a rvt file, etc.). The information that should be included in the BIM file is:

- General information: Location, address,
- Geometry: spaces distribution,
- Envelope materials: walls, roofs, ceilings, floors,
- Lighting system: location, geometry, type, power (W),
- HVAC system: production, distribution and terminal units elements and features,
- Other equipment: PCs, printers, elevators.

2- Dynamic monitoring data on CH performance. The DT collects, visualises and exploits real time data on building performance. There are several means for data collection. The DT system can connect to the monitoring system or BACS in the CH building using MQTT, API, etc. We can discuss the situation for every pilot. The data set size depends on the pilot size and monitoring level. It is recommended to collect data every 5 minutes. The data collected for the first pillar (energy and comfort) is:

- Outdoor environment: the system should monitor outdoor temperature, humidity, and solar radiation in the location of the CH.
- Indoor environment: temperature, humidity and CO₂ should be measured for each room while others variables such as lighting level could be also measured depending on the pilot

3 – Energy, IEQ and Pathologies performance models to calculate scores and carry out what-if analysis. The BIM models are developed with Python & EnergyPlus files (.py, .idf).

Output data

The digital twin developed at INHERIT offers the following outputs:

1. Visualisation of real-time and historical energy and indoor environment quality monitoring data in the BIM model and navigation panel (values & heatmaps displays in the BIM model; graphs display in the control panel²).
2. Energy and IEQ alarms displayed in the BIM models and control panel (e.g. lights were on last night in room XX, you have wasted X €).
3. Energy and IEQ dynamic scores displayed in the BIM model (values & heat maps) and the navigation/control panel (graphs).
4. Reference optimally operated and maintained CH building consumption (in kWh) displayed in the navigation/control panel and compared to the real CH building (graphs).
5. Energy consumption savings (in kWh, €, %, etc.) corresponding to a potential conservation measure or scenario displayed in the navigation/control panel (graphs).

² The definition of control panel can be found in section 4.3.4.2 Frontend implementation.

6. Visualisation of pathologies through totems³ in the 3D visor and through an inventory in the control panel. (Figure 54)
7. Indicates the potential for moisture formation by condensation in a space.

4.3.3. Updated architecture & technical specification

The architecture remains the same as presented in the D4.1. As a reminder, Figure 42 provides a detailed overview of the architecture and the technologies employed in the digital twin service.

Figure 42: Digital twin architecture and technologies.

The technologies used include:

- **Kubernetes** is an open-source platform designed to automate deploying, scaling, and operating application containers.
- **Kafka** (Apache Kafka) is a distributed streaming platform for building real-time, event-driven applications. It enables high-speed data processing with guaranteed message order and reliability.
- **MongoDB** is a NoSQL database that stores flexible, JSON-like documents. It's ideal for unstructured data and allows fast iteration thanks to its schema-less design.

³ Totem: Visual reference marker within a BIM model that signals the location of a specific element.

- **PostgreSQL** is an open-source, SQL-based relational database with strong data integrity and scalability features. It's suitable for managing complex datasets in reliable environments.
- **Python** is a high-level language known for simplicity and readability. It's used for microservices, data processing, and rapid development with fewer errors.
- **React** is a JavaScript library for building dynamic and responsive UIs. Its component-based structure improves code reusability and development speed.
- **IndexedDB** is a browser API for storing large amounts of structured data locally. It enables offline functionality and syncs with the server when online.
- **Autodesk** (Autodesk Platform Services) provide cloud APIs for BIM model visualisation and management. This project uses the Data Management and Model Derivative APIs.
- **EnergyPlus** is a simulation engine for modeling building energy and water usage. It runs via terminal, processing input files to generate detailed output.

4.3.4. Implementation: second technology release

As established in the previous deliverable (D4.1), the service architecture is composed of the following layers: storage layer, messaging orchestrator layer, microservices layer and frontend layer. These layers have been structured and consolidated for implementation, clearly differentiating the backend components, responsible for logic, data management, databases and microservice, and the frontend components, responsible for the user interface and for direct interaction with the end user.

4.3.4.1. Backend implementation

The backend implementation has been structured into several steps:

1. **Data ingestion with Kafka:** To handle real-time data input, Apache Kafka is used as the messaging system. This technology decouples data production from consumption, enabling system scalability and improving fault tolerance. Sensor data is sent to different Kafka topics, which are later read by consumers for processing.
2. **Data cleaning and storage with Python:** This step involves processing the data using Python, where various cleaning tasks are performed, such as removing duplicates, handling missing values, and validating formats. The data is then transformed and prepared for storage in the appropriate database.
3. **Storage in a NoSQL database:** Once processed, the data is stored in a NoSQL database such as MongoDB. This type of database allows for flexible data schemas, making it ideal for handling semi-structured or unstructured data.
4. **Serving processed data through an API:** Finally, the processed data is served through an API, enabling integration with the frontend or other microservices. The API also includes authentication mechanisms to ensure secure access.

5. Microservices implementation: microservice is composed of four distinct modules: the climate module, the simulation module, the calibration module, and the KPI (Key Performance Indicators) module. Each module is designed to handle specific tasks within the service. Figure 43 shows, in simplified form, the process and information flow of the microservice.

Figure 43: Process and information flow of the microservice.

- Climate Module:** This module, developed in Python, aims to improve the accuracy of building energy simulations by using real and up-to-date weather data. Climatic variables such as temperature, humidity, and solar radiation have a direct impact on both energy consumption and indoor conditions, making accurate information essential.

Traditionally, these simulations rely on EPW (EnergyPlus Weather) files, which contain historical climate data for a specific location. However, these records may not reflect current weather conditions, which can affect the reliability of the simulation results.

To address this, the module connects to a database and retrieves recent data from a weather station installed on the building itself or, alternatively, from a nearby station. The collected data includes global and horizontal radiation, air temperature, relative humidity, and atmospheric pressure.

Based on these measurements, the module calculates derived variables such as dew point temperature, direct normal radiation, and diffuse horizontal radiation. All this

updated information overwrites the corresponding values in the original EPW file. As a result, a new EPW file is generated, reflecting real and current climate conditions. This process is executed automatically every 15 days.

- **Simulation Module:** This module, developed in Python, uses EnergyPlus as the simulation engine to accurately simulate the energy performance of buildings. The engine runs through jEPlus parameterisation tool and is controlled directly by the Python module. EnergyPlus is specifically designed to simulate, among other things, the energy consumption and demand associated with heating, cooling, ventilation, lighting, domestic hot water, and other internal loads.

This module simulates both the reference building model and the parameterised model.

- **Reference building model:** Represents an idealized version of the building, where both operation and maintenance are assumed to be in optimal condition. It serves as a benchmark for evaluating the energy efficiency of the actual building.
 - **Parameterised model:** Represents the version resulting from parameterising the manually calibrated model. It includes variables that can be adjusted for calibration. This model is simulated several times using different combinations of parameters. The results are passed to the calibration module, which identifies the parameter sets that best reproduce the observed energy behaviour. The actual calibration process is performed in a separate module.
- **Calibration Module:** This module, developed in Python, is responsible for comparing the results of all simulations generated by the simulation module with the real data stored in the database, in order to select the simulation that best reflects the building's actual performance. To achieve this, it applies the Goodness of Fit (GOF) analytical method, as shown in Figure 44.

This method assesses the degree of similarity between the simulated results and the real data, assigning a score to each parameter set based on its accuracy. The optimal configuration is then automatically identified, the one with the lowest GOF value, indicating the best fit to the real behaviour of the building.

This module runs every 15 days, using the most recent 15 days of sensor data.

$$GOF = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \sqrt{NMBE^2 + CVRMSE^2} = \begin{cases} NMBE = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^N (y_i^* - \hat{y}_i)}{(N-1)y^*} \\ CVRMSE = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=0}^N (y_i^* - \hat{y}_i)^2}{N-1}}}{y^*} \end{cases}$$

Figure 44: GOF's formula.

This formula is composed of two indicators:

- **NMBE** (Normalized Mean Bias Error): measures the average bias of the model, that is, whether predictions tend to overestimate or underestimate the actual values.

CVRMSE (Coefficient of Variation of the Root Mean Square Error): represents the variation of the normalized root mean square error and reflects the dispersion of errors, indicating how far, on average, the predictions deviate from the actual values.

- **KPI Module:** This module, developed in Python, is responsible for calculating the building's energy efficiency indicators by comparing the results of the calibrated energy model with those of the reference model. These indicators assess the energy performance in each zone of the building, providing customized values both locally and at the whole-building level.

The process, which includes the recalibration of the energy model, the simulation of the reference building, and the calculation of the indicators, is fully automated. This enables the generation of a dynamic value that is periodically updated based on the building's actual usage.

The formula used to calculate the various indicators is as follows:

$$\text{Indicator (\%)} = \frac{\text{Reference building consumption (kWh)}}{\text{Calibrated building consumption (kWh)}} \times 100$$

Figure 45: Indicator's formula.

The indicators deliver two types of results: a current value, based on the past 15 days, and an estimated value, which predicts performance for the upcoming 15 days.

The scoring system is interpreted as follows:

- 100 % - 90 %: High energy efficiency.
- 90 % - 80 %: Medium energy efficiency.
- 80% -70%: Acceptable energy efficiency.
- Below 70%: Low energy efficiency.

Some of the indicators evaluated include equipment, fan coils, ventilation, lighting, and a global indicator representing the building's overall performance.

- **Pathologies Module:** It is a Python-based simulation module currently under development. It is expected to focus on the simulation of building pathologies.

These modules are bundled into three functional packages, which represent the final output provided by the service. The packages are as follows:

1. **Energy efficiency.** Executes simulations to evaluate energy-saving strategies. It compares a reference model to the real model and presents performance indicators, scores, and alerts when deviations are detected.
2. **Monitoring.** Displays real-time data through visual tools such as heatmaps and time series charts. It also manages alert systems to detect abnormal behaviour in building operation.
3. **Pathologies.** In development. It will include features for visualizing pathologies directly in the BIM model, maintaining an inventory, supporting scenario analysis, and generating alerts based on condition tracking or predictive analytics.
4. **Alarms.** Although this is an independent package, it is linked to the three previous packages. There are alarms related to energy efficiency, monitoring, and pathology detection. These alerts are displayed both in the 3D viewer and in the control panel, warning when unusual behaviour is detected.
The alarms may be triggered by various factors, such as faulty sensor readings, indoor conditions outside optimal ranges, or potential condensation risks in specific areas of the building.

4.3.4.2. Frontend implementation

1. **Market study:** A market study was conducted to analyse digital twin designs from other companies. It revealed that many contain too much information or use excessive or insufficient colour, which can overwhelm or disengage users. The first mock-up design will aim to address these issues.
2. **Mock-up design:** A visual prototype of the final frontend design was created to define the visual structure and user experience of the application. An example of these mock-ups can be seen in Figure 46, which shows, in general, how the information will be displayed in the navigation panel.

Figure 46: Navigation panel mock-up.

3. Development of initial UI interfaces: The first user interface (Figure 47) components were developed to interact with the API, display data, and provide functionality to the user. These include:

1. **3D viewer:** allows the visualisation of data in a three-dimensional environment.
2. **Control panel:** organized according to the different packages that make up the digital twin. Through this panel, users can navigate the various sections, select, and view the desired information.

Figure 47: Digital twin interface

The 3D viewer consists of a **three-dimensional interface** displaying the building's geometry. A BIM model is loaded into the viewer, allowing users to access static information about any element simply by clicking on it.

Figure 48 shows the **tools panel**, which includes the following functionalities:

1. First Person. Allows you to navigate through the model in first-person view.
2. Rotate Enables rotation of the model.
3. Framing. Adjusts the framing of the model in the viewport.
4. Camera Intersection. Allows creation of custom camera views.
5. Zoom window. Zooms in or out within a selected area of the model.
6. Measure. Measures the distance between two points.
7. Section analysis. Enables the creation of sections within the model.
8. Levels. Displays and separates the building by floors or levels.
9. Document browser. Lists the uploaded documents associated with the model.
10. Explode model. Breaks down the model into its components for better visualisation.
11. Model browser. Shows a list of all loaded models.
12. Properties. Displays the static properties of a selected element.
13. Settings. Allows configuration of the model's visualisation preferences.
14. Full screen. Displays the model in full-screen mode.

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The **control panel** is located on the right side of the viewer. Further to the right, there is an additional column displaying icons that represent the different packages included in the digital twin for this pilot. In this case, the first three visible icons correspond to the **monitoring, energy efficiency, and pathology packages**. Figure 50 shows how they are organized within the interface.

Figure 50: Control panel.

The front-end of these packages is currently under development, so there are some mock-ups and components already implemented. However, their appearance within the digital twin could be modified in the future as the project progresses.

The front-end part of the monitoring package is the most advanced (Figure 50-51); if the building is fully monitored, all floors will be displayed, and if it is only partially monitored, only the areas with installed sensors will be shown. This panel will include filtering options and an alarm section that will notify users in case of data reception errors or abnormal sensor readings. When selecting a zone and clicking on a specific sensor, the relevant information for that device will appear; as shown in Figure 51, for example, a sensor measuring indoor temperature on floor P0 will display a time-series graph of temperature evolution, the day's minimum and maximum values, and the current temperature recorded on that floor.

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Figure 51: Monitoring package in the control panel (I)

Figure 52: Monitoring package in the control panel (II)

Regarding the energy efficiency and pathology packages (Figures 53-54), mock-ups are currently being developed to determine the most effective way to visually present the outputs of each package. Some preliminary versions of these designs are shown below; however, the final version of their integration and visualisation within the digital twin will be included in D4.3.

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Figure 53: Mock-up of the front-end of the energy efficiency package in the control panel.

Figure 54: Mock-up of the front-end of the pathology package in the control panel.

4.3.5. Deployment

For the deployment of the service in the pilot sites, technical meetings are necessary to define the specific expectations of each case. These sessions aim to establish the main focus of the service, be it cultural heritage surveillance, pathology monitoring or preventive maintenance.

In addition, technical information is collected for each pilot, including key characteristics, current conditions and any other relevant data to properly configure the system.

4.3.5.1. Spanish pilot

The Spanish pilot is being developed at the Monastery of *Nuestra Señora del Prado*, a historic building whose origins date back to 1440. Currently, the site covers an approximate area of 55,258 m² and houses the central offices of the Departments of Culture, Tourism, Sports, and Education of the Regional Government of Castilla y León.

Given the size and complexity of the building, it has been defined that the digital twin will cover the church, office areas, sacristy, and the Praves cloister.

This pilot is structured into three main packages: the monitoring package, the energy efficiency package, and the pathology package.

For the monitoring package, three Netatmo sensors will be installed to measure indoor environmental quality (IEQ) in the office area, the sacristy, and the church. These sensors will collect data on temperature, humidity, CO₂ concentration, and noise levels (dB) with a near real-time sampling frequency (every 5 minutes). Outdoor environmental conditions will be monitored through a weather API.

Due to the high level of heritage protection of the building, the installation of other types of sensors is not permitted. As a result, it is not possible to monitor energy consumption or the structural condition of the walls.

Regarding the pathology package, the focus will be on analysing potential condensation dampness issues. To this end, exterior temperature and humidity sensors will be employed in order to carry out a predictive analysis of the issue, particularly in the sacristy. This area, frequently used for exhibitions, contains murals that could be damaged by moisture.

As part of the energy efficiency package, energy models of the building are developed directly within our Digital Twin using SketchUp, and simulations are carried out through EnergyPlus. These models will first be manually calibrated using the building's energy bills and then automatically calibrated through a Python script that tests different combinations of input parameters to produce a model that best matches the building's real performance.

The monitoring package will generate heat maps with colour scales to represent the sensor data, highlighting whether the values are within acceptable or critical ranges. The locations of the sensors

will be shown in the digital viewer, accompanied by time-series graphs of the collected data and future projections. An alarm panel will also be included to flag any anomalous values.

Regarding the energy efficiency package, the output will include comparative graphs between the real performance of the building and a reference model. Additionally, indicators will be generated to assess the building's energy performance based on that reference.

Meanwhile, the pathology package will simulate different condensation scenarios. This approach will help anticipate risks to the exposed artworks.

4.3.5.2. Polish pilot

The Polish pilot is being carried out in a residential building located in Gdynia, with an approximate area of 1,168 m². Built in 1928, just two years before the official founding of the city, the building stands out for its modernist architecture, a unique style that is rarely preserved today.

This pilot will focus on the following DT packages: monitoring, energy efficiency, pathologies, and potentially also accessibility.

For the monitoring package, two Netatmo sensors have been installed in two of the twelve apartments that make up the building. These sensors will measure the indoor environmental quality of the selected apartments, recording data on temperature, humidity, CO₂ concentration and sound levels (dB) with a near real-time sampling frequency (every 5 minutes). Outdoor environmental conditions will be monitored through a meteorological API.

Although the building is listed as cultural heritage, it is still a residential property, making it difficult to install additional sensors in other apartments.

Regarding the pathology package, the focus will be on the development of a visual inventory of the building's potential pathologies. This will be accessible from the digital viewer via an information totem. As in the Spanish pilot, an analysis of potential condensation and dampness problems will also be carried out.

For the energy efficiency package, the same steps defined in the Spanish pilot will be followed: the generation of energy models in SketchUp, simulation using EnergyPlus, and calibration through Python scripts, which automatically adjust parameters to ensure the model closely resembles the real behaviour of the building, all performed inside the Digital Twin environment.

As a result, the monitoring package will provide heat maps, time-series graphs with future projections, visualisation of sensor locations in the digital viewer, and an alert system for abnormal values. The pathology package will deliver a detailed inventory of building issues and simulations of potential condensation scenarios. The energy efficiency package will include comparison graphs between the real performance of the building and a reference model, as well as performance indicators based on that reference.

Finally, the accessibility package will highlight accessible elements within the 3D model by applying different colours according to their accessibility level.

4.4. s.7 Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns

4.4.1. Service overview

As part of the INHERIT project's monitoring, operation and management services, the Real-time Insights on Activity and Mobility Patterns service (s.7) is **designed to offer continuous and actionable information regarding occupancy and movement within buildings**. The service offers continuous monitoring of crowd movement, presence, and indoor climate conditions within buildings. It equips facility managers with a dynamic dashboard that provides centralized visibility into how buildings are used and how indoor environmental quality evolves throughout the day. The service is designed to react in real time when overcrowding occurs or when indoor environmental quality (IEQ) indicators reach critical thresholds, by sending alerts to the facility managers. Overall, through advanced data collection and visualisation, the service can support not only comfort-based room reallocation, but also strategic use cases such as evacuation planning.

Although the service is still under development, the frontend implementation has been completed and connected to simulated data sources that mimic live sensor input. This allows realistic validation of system behaviour and user interaction. The integration of the live backend feed and final alerting system is the primary remaining step before the final release. Once deployed, the service will operate as a real-time decision support tool across INHERIT pilot buildings.

Figure 55 presents the landing page of the service (available at <https://insights-inherit.euinno.eu/>), which provides the centralized, user-friendly interface where key indicators such as historical and **real-time crowd monitoring, energy usage trends and alerts are immediately visible**.

Figure 55: Landing page of s.7

4.4.2. Input & output data

Input data

The service operates on a steady flow of high-frequency input data originating from IoT sensors distributed throughout the pilot buildings. These sensors track both occupancy-related metrics and indoor environmental parameters. The key input data types include:

- room-level occupancy (people count),
- movement detection for mobility analysis,
- indoor climate metrics such as temperature, humidity, CO₂ concentration, light levels, noise, and room energy usage.

The complete data pipeline begins at the sensor level. Sensors transmit data via MQTT to a dedicated data ingestion layer, where a Python-based service subscribes to the relevant MQTT topics. This service handles initial data parsing, preprocessing, and writes the processed records to a PostgreSQL database. Finally, the data is exposed to the real-time monitoring service via a robust REST API, allowing the frontend to retrieve and display it with minimal latency.

Output data

The service's output is presented as a combination of numerical insights and visual analytics. These include the real-time occupancy status of each room, the total occupancy of a building, energy consumption trends, environmental comfort indicators, and alerts when thresholds are breached.

These insights are delivered through an intuitive web-based dashboard that includes per-building summaries, per-room detail views, historical metric charts, and contextual recommendations.

The ultimate goal of these outputs is to support building administrators and facility managers in making informed, proactive decisions. Real-time occupancy information enables space optimization and safety management (e.g., avoiding overcrowding, reallocating underused areas). Energy consumption and comfort indicators drive efficiency improvements, helping reduce costs and carbon footprint while maintaining healthy indoor conditions. Historical metrics allow trend analysis and predictive maintenance planning, while alerts provide immediate, actionable warnings that prevent risks from escalating. Together, these insights transform raw sensor data into actionable intelligence for smarter, safer, and more sustainable building operations.

4.4.3. Updated architecture & technical specification

The updated architecture of the service builds upon the same layered concept as delivered in D4.1, but it has been restructured into a more robust pipeline. While the original model already separated sensing, processing, and visualization, the **updated implementation introduces clear interfaces, stronger decoupling, and dedicated APIs** that make the system easier to maintain, scale, and extend.

In the sensing layer, infrared and environmental devices continue to provide real-time measurements, but instead of being sent directly to a processing unit, they now publish to an MQTT broker via Wi-Fi and LoRa gateways. This message-driven backbone improves reliability and resilience, since data can be buffered, replayed, or scaled across multiple subscribers. In the processing and storage layer, an Ingestion API subscribes to the MQTT topics, performs preprocessing (such as filtering, unit normalization, and timestamp validation), and enriches the payloads with contextual metadata (e.g., floor or room identifiers). The cleaned data is then persisted into a PostgreSQL database, which serves as the long-term system of record. On top of the database, the Central REST API provides controlled access to the stored information, offering endpoints for querying historical time-series, aggregations, and latest sensor values. By separating ingestion from data access, the architecture not only isolates concerns but also allows secure, scalable access patterns for external clients and dashboards. In parallel, an Alerts Service continuously monitors incoming values against predefined rules and thresholds (for example, indoor environmental quality limits or occupancy constraints). When conditions are violated, alerts are generated in real time. Although the dedicated Alerts API for distributing these notifications to external consumers is still under development and planned for the final project deliverable, the alerting mechanism has already been designed and integrated into the processing pipeline, ensuring that the system will be able to provide timely warnings once the API is released. Finally, the Visualization Layer has been strengthened through a dedicated frontend application that consumes both the Data API and the Alerts API. This allows real-time dashboards to present occupancy details and IEQ visualizations, while simultaneously receiving live notifications when thresholds are breached.

Overall, while not fundamentally different from the earlier three-layer structure, the updated architecture is more robust, modular, and aligned with best practices for distributed data systems. It introduces reliable messaging, persistent storage, and well-defined APIs, thereby ensuring scalability, maintainability, and a clear path for future extensions.

Figure 56: Updated architecture of s.7

4.4.4. Implementation: second technology release

The second release of s.7 includes significant progress on the visual and functional frontend, ensuring that the system is user-ready once live data becomes available. In more details, the current implementation supports all core flows including building and room selection, real-time sensor value rendering, historical trend visualisation, and occupancy aggregation at room and building levels, using synthetic data. The service will connect with the real-time data through the REST API once the crowd monitoring sensors are deployed at the pilot sites.

4.4.4.1. Backend implementation

The service consumes sensor data which are collected by the Data Exchange Platform. **The data become available by consuming the central REST API**, following predefined data models, using typical HTTP requests. Originally the data are exposed in MQTT topics from the sensors and different custom APIs have been developed to collect, preprocess and store the data in the PostgreSQL database optimized for time-series analysis. In this direction, a s.7 dedicated API was developed to collect data from the crowd monitoring sensors. The API was developed in Python, using the FastAPI

framework, following the OpenAPI specifications. This component subscribes to the MQTT topics, published by the building sensors, processes incoming data streams (e.g., validation, enrichment with room and building identifiers), and stores the structured information into the relational database.

This service currently interfaces exclusively with this central REST API to query live room metrics, occupancy levels, environmental readings, and historical trends. A background alerting engine, currently under development, will also query this database, compare sensor values against predefined thresholds, and generate alerts, which will be exposed through the API and visualised in the frontend. All backend components are containerized using Docker and orchestrated with Kubernetes, ensuring scalable, fault-tolerant deployment across pilot environments.

4.4.4.2. Frontend implementation

The Real-time Insights on Activity and Mobility Patterns service is currently under active development, with the frontend application already near completion. Developed using the React framework, the frontend is designed to provide an intuitive, responsive interface that visualises real-time data related to occupancy and mobility patterns in smart buildings. Although it is currently operating with synthetic data, the interface reflects the complete user experience and will seamlessly integrate with real-time data streams in the final version.

Upon login, the user lands on the main navigation pane, where the monitoring dashboard, serving as the entry point into the real-time monitoring data, can be accessed. As presented in Figure 57, this module displays high-level metrics such as the total number of buildings, current occupancy rate, and cumulative energy usage for the day. Below these summary indicators, the system presents a grid of building cards, each showing live values for occupancy and energy consumption, along with their classification tags (e.g., Office, University). Users can filter buildings by category and search for specific facilities, simulating a responsive and scalable design intended to support large deployments.

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Figure 57: Monitoring dashboard of s.7

Clicking on any building card brings the user to a building-level view, displayed in Figure 58. This screen is structured to show three major sections: general building information (including some building-level aggregated metrics), building-level occupancy breakdown per room, and a summary of real-time sensor. These include people count, temperature, humidity, CO₂ concentration, noise levels, light levels, and energy consumption, each compared against pre-defined optimal ranges. Colour indicators highlight whether the current conditions are optimal, out of range, or within acceptable thresholds.

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Figure 58: s.7 Building-level view

The user can drill down even further by selecting individual rooms from the building-level view (Figure 58). This brings them to a room-level monitoring interface where a detailed breakdown of the room's sensor configuration is presented. For each metric, the current value is shown, alongside status tags and a direct link to view historical data. This historical data is rendered either using interactive charts, which support time-based navigation and overlay the optimal value range for easy comparison, or in a tabular format showing the exact measurement at each timestamp.

Figure 59: s.7 Room-level view

4.4.5. Deployment

The deployment of the service to the pilot premises is executed through a bifurcated parallel procedure comprising two concurrent operational processes. The conceptual rationale on following this parallel process is that the same type of sensors that will be used on the pilot premises are already installed at SLG's offices. Thus, the first process was to install the sensors at the pilot premises, and the second process was to receive, transform, and store the data from the sensors at SLG premises, as the same type of hardware was used.

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The first process required several technical on-site meetings with the pilot's administrators to their sites to come up with a plan for the installation of the sensors. The end goal of the conducted plan was to effectively meet the technical requirements while preserving the cultural heritage.

While the described process was ongoing, the second had already started to take place as well. The technical description of this process is described in Section 4.4.4.

5. ‘Preservation & maintenance’ services

5.1. s.8 Preventive Maintenance with H-BIM

5.1.1. Service overview

INHERIT's Service 8 proposes a **preventive conservation methodology** based on the **integration of technical inspections and H-BIM**. Unlike a reactive approach, this methodology promotes planned, proactive, and sustainable maintenance of built heritage.

The main objective of the service is to **systematize the collection, digitization, and management of technical information related to historic buildings through HBIM models** enriched with historical, construction, and pathological data. This approach allows for **preventive action planning, resource optimization**, and above all, the **preservation of the authenticity and cultural value** of heritage assets.

The service aims to build a **comprehensive digital environment** in which all relevant information for building conservation, from geometry and materials to conservation status, pathologies, and past interventions, can be integrated, visualized, and updated. In this context, the HBIM model acts as a **structured and linked data repository**, capable of **associating technical, documentary, and diagnostic information with real architectural elements**, thereby **facilitating decision-making and future planning based on risk and criticality criteria**, following principles established by the *Spanish National Preventive Conservation Plan (IPCE)*. According to this plan, preventive conservation must be based on the identification, assessment, and control of risks, focusing actions on their root causes, and implementing systematic monitoring and control protocols, tailored to available resources and oriented toward minimizing invasive interventions (IPCE,2011).

Figure 60: Methodological process of s.8: from multiscale data collection to integration into an enriched HBIM model, supporting preventive maintenance planning.

The application of preventive conservation strategies is especially relevant in the heritage context, where **buildings feature unique characteristics: traditional materials, non-standard construction**

systems, complex geometries, and multiple evolutionary layers accumulated over time, due to successive construction phases and historical interventions driven by changing functional needs. These singularities complicate the direct application of standard digital methodologies, such as the BIM used in new or recent construction. Therefore, this service proposes a **specific, technically complex, and carefully adapted approach tailored to the heritage context**.

This approach is essential to ensure the system’s feasibility, as the modelling of a 20th century concrete and steel residential building, such as the Polish pilot, is not comparable to that of a historic ensemble like the Monastery of Nuestra Señora del Prado, whose construction began in the 14th century using ashlar masonry and rammed earth, and which has undergone documented transformations to this day.

5.1.2. Input & output data

The development of this service relies on a diverse set of data that must be collected, interpreted, and incorporated into the H-BIM model to support effective preventive management of built heritage. These data constitute the necessary inputs for building a rich, functional, and operational information model.

Input Data

The input data can be classified into the following categories:

- **Geometric data:** surveys using laser scanning, point clouds, photogrammetry, and historical plans. These inputs enable the generation of a precise 3D representation of the asset.
 - In Annex I, the technical data collection form completed by both pilots is included, documenting the accuracy and methodology applied during scanning and point cloud processing.

Figure 61: Integration of geometric data in the HBIM model, combining point clouds and detailed modelling to capture the architectural complexity of heritage elements.

- **Construction data:** information about structural systems, traditional materials, construction techniques, and unique heritage components, obtained both in situ and from documentary or archival sources.
- **Diagnostic data:** pathological symptoms, identified causes, conservation status, and urgency of intervention. This information is collected through the technical inspection methodology developed under WP3-T3.1, described in Deliverable D3.2 – Second INHERIT Assessment &

Monitoring Framework, Section 2. The data are recorded through structured digital forms interoperable with the HBIM environment.

Figure 62: Technical inspection workflow and its alignment with the H-BIM model for preventive maintenance.

- **Historical and documentary data:** information on construction phases, past interventions, original uses, and the building's transformation over time. This data helps contextualize conservation decisions in terms of authenticity and integrity.
- **Data on installations and functional performance:** information on HVAC, lighting, ventilation, evacuation, and comfort systems, when available.
- **Environmental or monitoring data:** where permitted, sensor data on humidity, temperature, deformation, or other relevant parameters may be included.

As part of the INHERIT project, *Netatmo Indoor Air Quality sensors* have been installed in the pilot buildings where Service 8 is planned to be deployed. These devices enable the continuous monitoring of environmental conditions, such as CO₂ concentration, temperature, humidity, and noise levels, providing valuable input for assessing potential risks and supporting preventive conservation actions.

Output data

The expected outputs of the service take the form of structured information layers that support preventive management of the heritage building:

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- **Enriched HBIM model:** 3D model in Revit at LOD 300–350⁴, structured by categories, families, and parameters defined according to conservation needs. Includes architectural, structural, and installation elements.
- **Semantic data association:** each model element is linked to technical, historical, and conservation attributes that describe its condition, behaviour, and relevance.
- **Graphical and interactive diagnostics:** direct visualization of pathologies and conservation status through the model, with information layers that include inspection forms, priorities, and review frequencies, using native Revit functionalities and plugins, such as Dynamo, to support decision-making and maintenance planning.
- **Intervention log:** historical record of maintenance, restoration, or modification actions associated with each component.
- **Preventive maintenance plan:** recommendations based on risk, criticality, and review frequency, generated from the structured data in the model.
- **Interoperable model:** exportable in open formats (IFC) for integration with other systems (e.g., GIS platforms, digital twins, or energy management services).

The service is entirely developed within the Autodesk Revit environment, using its built-in features and data structure capabilities. No additional interface or external platform is developed, in order to prioritize practical applicability, integration with existing workflows, and long-term usability.

5.1.3. Updated architecture & technical specification

Despite the growing adoption of digitalisation in the built heritage sector, the practical application of HBIM still faces significant limitations. Unlike conventional BIM in new construction, HBIM lacks a fully operational and standardised methodology that addresses the material, morphological, and historical singularities of cultural assets. Historic buildings often feature **unique architectural elements, irregular geometries, stratified construction layers, and traditional building systems that defy industrial logic**. As a result, standard modelling and classification approaches become inadequate. Within this context, INHERIT's Service 8 aims to develop **a data architecture tailored to heritage conservation needs, with a clear focus on preventive management**. This architecture is aligned with the principles defined in the *buildingSMART User Guide for Cultural Heritage (Doc. 14)* and the methodological H-BIM recommendations of the *Spanish research project CAREEN*:

⁴ LOD (Level of Development) indicates the level of geometric precision, semantic richness, and documentation detail in BIM elements—LOD 300 provides accurate geometry for coordination, while LOD 350 includes detailed connections for maintenance planning. However, in heritage contexts, achieving these thresholds is particularly challenging due to the complexity, historical stratification, and artisanal variability of building elements. Rafael Martín Talaverano et al. (2021) propose extending the concept with LOK (Level of Knowledge) to evaluate the information completeness and confidence in historical models, highlighting the need for adapted taxonomies to reflect the uncertainty inherent in cultural heritage data.

Development of AI-based methods for damage characterization in historic constructions through 3D point clouds.

5.1.3.1. H-BIM project Architecture

The technical architecture has been implemented using Autodesk Revit, leveraging its native capabilities for model organisation, linking, and federation. Each disciplinary domain (**Architecture, MEP, Pathologies, and Maintenance**) has been developed as an **independent submodel (.rvt) and coordinated via a master federated file**. This setup enables parallel work, discipline-specific control, and full traceability of technical data. This approach follows the general modelling philosophy set out in the BIM User Guide for Cultural Heritage (buildingSMART Spanish Chapter, 2020), which promotes consistency, semantic structure, and adaptability in HBIM practices

The project structure includes:

- A **master coordination** file for planning and cross-checking
- Four thematic **submodels: Architecture, MEP, Pathologies, Maintenance**
- **Linked** point clouds, 2D drawings, and external documentation (e.g., DWG, PDF)

Figure 63: HBIM structure used in Service 8: submodels for Architecture, MEP, Pathologies, and Maintenance (left) and model integration with point cloud data (Pilot 6, right)

5.1.3.2. Data Model structure and information levels

The HBIM data model developed for Service 8 is a **structured alphanumeric system** that organises the technical, material, and diagnostic information of the building elements. In this context, **a data model defines how information is structured, classified, and associated to each architectural component**, enabling its use for preventive conservation planning.

The model follows a hierarchical logic: **Category → Family → Parameters**, allowing for structured, filterable, and semantically rich representations of the building fabric. Each physical element (e.g., wall, column, arch) is assigned to a general category, instantiated as a family, and defined through a tailored set of parameters. These parameters include geometric, material, pathological, and maintenance-related attributes, in line with the goals of Service 8.

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This structure not only supports standard BIM logic, but also responds to the inspection “headings” system developed in WP3 (Task 3.1), which classifies architectural elements based on their functional and typological role in the building.

Figure 64: HBIM Data modelling logic: from category to family and parameter level.

Figure 65: HBIM model (Architecture and MEP sub-models). Office area: general view and section. *Work in progress.*

Beyond the parameter-level definition, the model incorporates a **second semantic layer through the classification of information into seven thematic levels**. These levels group and standardise data associated with each construction element according to their type and purpose within the preventive conservation workflow:

1. Material composition
2. Construction system
3. Pathologies and degradation mechanisms
4. Historical and semantic information
5. Maintenance actions (past/planned)

6. Inspection records
7. Monitoring and environmental conditions

These information levels are essential to support preventive conservation strategies: they allow **assessing the building's condition, identifying risks, and planning tailored interventions based on real data.**

Figure 66: Information structure based on 7 key data levels. These are used to assess the conservation state of the building and support management decisions.

The structure and content of these information levels are inspired by the recommendations proposed by the CAREEN project (UPM, 2023), which address semantic depth and HBIM data modelling in preventive conservation scenarios

While all sub-models are integrated into a common HBIM structure, **not all data levels are present or relevant in every submodel.** For example, *semantic or historical information* (Level 4) is primarily associated with architectural components, whereas *maintenance records or monitoring data* (Levels 5–7) are linked to elements from the pathology and MEP models.

This structure follows a **hierarchical and functional logic**: each submodel (Architecture, MEP, Maintenance/Pathologies) contains only the parameters and information levels required to describe its domain-specific elements. This selective approach optimises the model's usability, improves performance, and prevents data redundancy, while preserving semantic consistency across the federated environment.

Figure 67: Relationship between HBIM submodels and data layers defined in Service 8.

This data model structure, developed for building-scale HBIM applications, also **demonstrates strong potential for scalability to other contexts and spatial levels**. A clear example of this was observed during the peer-learning visit to the Baraccano historical complex in Bologna (June 2025), where similar methodological principles were applied at an urban scale. In Baraccano, the use of low-resolution HBIM models, integrated with GIS tools and the Italian Carta del Rischio (risk mapping strategy), supports proactive maintenance and long-term resource planning across multiple buildings and public spaces.

This confirms that the structured, layered approach defined in Service 8, based on information levels, parameter logic, and preventive strategies, can be adapted for use beyond individual buildings. It offers a **flexible framework for multi-scalar heritage management, facilitating interoperability between technical data, public policy, and community engagement initiatives**. The experience in Baraccano strengthens the transferability of Service 8's principles to more complex heritage settings, such as neighborhoods or historic urban landscapes. This layered and scalable logic is also consistent with national heritage BIM guidelines such as those published for BIC-listed buildings in Spain (Gobierno de España - Ministerio de Cultura, 2021).

5.1.3.3. Element-Level Parameters

Each heritage component modelled in the HBIM (e.g., arch, column, vault) **is enriched with a structured set of parameters**, which form the semantic backbone of the Service 8 database. These parameters:

- **Describe** the geometric, material, and construction characteristics of the element
- **Associate** relevant documentation, historical records, or cultural values
- **Capture** the conservation status, diagnosed pathologies, and maintenance actions taken or planned

The parameter structure is tailored to the needs of preventive conservation and is aligned with the logic of the federated submodels (Architecture, MEP, Pathologies, Maintenance). It enables advanced querying, filtering, and analysis for planning inspections, prioritising interventions, and tracing changes over time.

Given the **complexity and uniqueness of heritage buildings**, the **parameter set was carefully designed to strike a balance between information richness, model performance, and data manageability**. This trade-off has also been explored in modelling protected modern buildings (García Moreno, 2024), confirming that the balance between precision, manageability, and conservation utility is a key HBIM design factor.

The number and type of parameters were optimised to avoid overloading the file, while ensuring that each element contains the essential information for decision-making.

To support this semantic framework, a **detailed list of parameters has been defined for each federated sub-model**.

The tables below outline the complete structure of these parameters, including their purpose, data type, IFC type, and correspondence with the seven information levels. This structure ensures semantic consistency across the model and allows future scalability for inspection and maintenance workflows.

Parameter Name	Description	Type	Inform. Level	IFC Entity
Arch_Element_Code	Unique identification code for the architectural element	Text	2	IfcBuildingElement
Arch_Element_Location	Spatial location or reference within the building ("north side aisle", "south façade")	Text	2	IfcBuildingElement
Arch_Element_Type	Element type (arch, wall, vault, etc.)	Text	2	IfcBuildingElement
Arch_Material	Primary construction material	Text	1	IfcMaterial
Arch_Construction_System	Wall/roof/arch assembly logic	Text		IfcElementAssembly

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Arch_Execution_Technique	Construction technique used in the execution of the element	Text	3	IfcBuildingElementProxy
Arch_Chronology	Historical period or construction phase	Text/ Enum	4	IfcBuildingElementProxy
Arch_Level_Of_Alteration	Degree of modification or authenticity	Enum (Low/Med/High)	4	IfcBuildingElementProxy
Arch_Heritage_Protection	Indicates whether the element is protected under local, national, or international heritage regulations	Yes/No	4	IfcBuildingElementProxy
Arch_Historical_Reference	Linked documentation or archive record	URL/ Text	4	IfcDocumentReference
Arch_Use	Original or current functional use	Text	4	IfcSpace
Arch_Shape_Description	Formal description (e.g., semicircular, ogival)	Text	2	IfcBuildingElementProxy

Table 14: Parameters of the Architecture sub-model elements

Parameter Name	Description	Type	Inform. Level	IFC Entity
MEP_System_Type	HVAC, Lighting, Plumbing, etc.	Enum	2	IfcSystem

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MEP_Status	Operational status (active, redundant, obsolete)	Enum	5	IfcDistributionElement
MEP_Location	Physical placement or routing note	Text	2	IfcDistributionElement
MEP_Maintenance_Access	Accessibility level	Enum	5	IfcDistributionElement
MEP_Last_Inspection_Date	Most recent inspection date	Date	6	IfcDistributionElement
MEP_Linked_Arch_Element	Related architectural element	Text	2	IfcRelConnectsElements

Table 15: Parameters of the MEP sub-model elements

Parameter Name	Description	Type	Inform. Level	IFC Entity
Pathology_Lesion_Type	Crack, moisture, biological growth, etc.	Enum	3	IfcAnnotation
Pathology_Lesion_Cause	Suspected or confirmed origin	Text	3	IfcAnnotation
Pathology_Severity	Criticality level	Enum (1–3)	3	IfcAnnotation
Pathology_Detailed_Symptom	Specific manifestation or appearance of the damage	Text	3	IfcAnnotation

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Pathology_Symptom_Location		Text	3	IfcAnnotation
Pathology_Location	Geometric description or elevation	Text	3	IfcAnnotation
Pathology_Detection_Date	Date of initial observation	Date	6	IfcAnnotation
Pathology_Inspector	Person/Team who recorded it	Text	6	IfcPerson
Pathology_Image_Ref	Linked visual documentation	URL/ Path	3	IfcDocumentReference

Table 16: Parameters of the Pathology sub-model elements

Parameter Name	Description	Type	Inform. Level	IFC Entity
Maint_Action_Type	Preventive, corrective, restorative	Enum	5	IfcTask
Maint_Action_Date	Date of last intervention	Date	5	IfcTaskTime
Maint_Last_Action_Log	Unique identification code of the latest intervention or maintenance action	Text	5	IfcTask
Maint_Frequency		Text	3	IfcAnnotation

Maint_Responsible_Agency	Who performed or authorized the work	Text	5	IfcOrganization
Maint_Documentation_Ref	Associated report, invoice, permit	URL/ Path	5	IfcDocumentReference
Maint_Inspection_Photo_Path	Link or reference to the most recent photo taken during the TI	Text	5	IfcTask
Maint_TI_Heading	Inspection category in which the element is assessed	Text	5	IfcTask
Maint_Recommendation	Suggested action from diagnosis	Text	5	IfcTask
Maint_Intervention_Required				
Maint_Priority	Based on risk and urgency	Enum (Low/Med/High)	5	IfcTask

Table 17: Parameters of the Maintenance sub-model elements

Each parameter in the tables above has been aligned, where applicable, with an official IFC entity defined in the IFC 4 schema (ISO 16739, 2013). This ensures semantic consistency, facilitates future data exchange in openBIM environments, and enhances model interoperability. A complete list of the IFC entity types relevant to Service 8 is provided in Annex II: IFC 4 Entities Relevant to Preventive Maintenance Modelling.

The following example illustrates this logic with a real-world application to an architectural element from the Spanish pilot:

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Submodel	Parameter Name	Example Value
Architecture	ElementCode	A0152
	ElementName	Semi-circular arch on pilasters at the ground floor of the Praves cloister
	ElementLocation	Ground floor, Praves Cloister, Monastery of Our Lady of Prado
	ConstructionPeriod	1440 (original structure); Renovated 1986â€”1989
	ConstructionSystem	Semi-circular arch
	ExecutionTechnique	Dressed limestone ashlar blocks
	HeritageProtection	Yes
	MaterialType	Campaspero limestone
	SpecificWeight	2.43 g/cm ³
	Density	2430 kg/m ³
	Porosity	3.77 %
	WaterAbsorption	6.24 %
	CompressiveStrength	74.17 MPa
	FlexuralStrength	6.24 MPa
	ElasticModulus	1233.13 MPa
	ThermalConductivity	No data
	ThermalTransmittance	No data
	AcousticProperties	No data
	FireResistance	Moderate
	ArchSpan	1.60 m
ArchRise	0.80 m	
ArchThickness	0.45 m	
PillarHeight	2.40 m	
PillarWidth	0.45 m	
CulturalInformationPath	Book/El Monasterio de Nuestra Señora de Prado-1997-ISBN: 84-7846-431-X	
HistoricalInformationPath	docs/Layouts-PravesCloister-1984-Restoration.pdf	
HistoricalPhotoPath	images/PravesCloister-1904.jpg	

Submodel	Parameter Name	Example Value
Pathologies + Inspection Data	MainSymptom	Fissures or cracks
	DetailedSymptom	Vertical cracks
	SymptomLocation	Close to a free edge of the wall
	LesionType	Lesions of the structure itself
	CauseDescription	Dilatation or heat contraction, or expansion or moisture retraction
Maintenance	ConservationState	Fair
	MaintenanceFrequency	Annual
	NextMaintenanceDate	15/06/2026
	RepairPriority	3
	InterventionRequired	Yes
	TechnicalInspectionHeading	Foundations, Facade and Structure
	LastMaintenanceLog	Scheduled visual inspection carried out on 19/06/2026
	RecentInterventions	Structural restoration and consolidation in 1989
	TechnicalSheetPath	docs/A0152_TechnicalSheet.pdf
	InspectionPhotoPath	images/A0152_VerticalCrack.jpg
AccessLevel	Easy access from courtyard	
RiskLevel	Medium	

Figure 68: Parametric and semantic definition of an architectural element (arch from the cloister of Nuestra Señora del Prado Monastery).

5.1.3.4. Technical Considerations and Challenges

The modelling process revealed several recurring challenges in HBIM for heritage contexts:

- **Non-standard geometries:** Heritage features such as vaults, arches, cornices, and decorative elements often require manual or mass-based modelling, limiting interoperability and automation.
- **Balancing precision and usability:** Over-modelling slows the platform; under-modelling omits relevant data. Custom graphic and semantic LOD criteria were defined per typology.

Figure 69: Point cloud sections and orthophotos used to support the modelling of architectural profiles and details.

- **Lack of HBIM standards:** The absence of shared international standards affects semantic consistency, requiring custom parameter structures per sub-model (yet IFC-compatible).

- **Variable data quality:** In many cases, original drawings were outdated or inaccurate, requiring point cloud-based modelling and detailed on-site verification.

5.1.4. Implementation: second technology release

5.1.4.1. Backend implementation

The backend logic of Service 8 is **fully implemented within the Autodesk Revit** HBIM environment, without requiring the development of a standalone software or external database. The system is based on a **federated model architecture**, where each domain (Architecture, MEP, Pathologies, Maintenance) is developed as an **independent (.rvt)** sub-model and coordinated through a master file.

Key aspects of the backend implementation include:

- **Structured data** modelling based on a custom parameter dictionary aligned with IFC4 types and preventive maintenance logic.
- **Integration of 7 defined information levels** to store technical, material, historical, and diagnostic data.
- **Semantic enrichment** of HBIM elements with structured attributes such as symptoms, interventions, inspection dates and documentation links.
- **Establishment of data workflows** for importing external resources, such as documentation, inspection forms or sensor readings.
- Preparation of the model for **automation processes** using tools like Dynamo, enabling advanced queries, risk filtering, and condition-based maintenance planning.
- **Compatibility** with IFC export standards to **facilitate integration** with openBIM tools, FM systems or digital twins. The H-BIM model will be shared with the developers of INHERIT Service 1 and Service 6 to enable their respective implementations.

5.1.4.2. Frontend implementation

The frontend implementation of Service 8 **does not involve the development of a dedicated interface or dashboard**. Instead, it is **fully embedded within the Autodesk Revit environment**, making use of its native capabilities to support querying, visualization, and analysis of preventive maintenance data.

Users interact directly with the HBIM model through Revit tools such as:

- **Filtered views and graphic overrides** to highlight pathologies, priorities, and risk levels
- **Schedules and legends to display parameter data** (e.g., next inspection, damage severity, maintenance frequency)
- **Linked documentation and exportable reports** in table or diagram formats
- Semantic filtering and grouping based on sub-models and inspection outcomes

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This embedded approach ensures full compatibility with standard architectural and heritage workflows, while **avoiding the complexity of developing and maintaining custom interfaces**.

The following diagram outlines the complete cycle, from initial model enrichment and technical inspection, to user-driven queries and decision-support outputs. Users access the federated HBIM model, select elements or parameters of interest, and generate visual or tabular outputs from real-time semantic data. The system allows for continuous updates based on inspection and maintenance feedback.

Figure 70: User interaction and data analysis workflow in Service 8. From HBIM enrichment and inspection data input to semantic queries and maintenance outputs, fully integrated in the Revit environment

Outputs are generated on demand and include visual alerts, maintenance planning, intervention prioritisation, and reports on the conservation status of the asset. These functionalities are fully integrated into the HBIM file, enabling a practical and streamlined deployment of Service 8 in real heritage management contexts. This approach is in line with HBIM training and management models like those proposed by Adami et al. (2023), which highlight the usefulness of embedding maintenance workflows within the modelling environment.

5.1.5. Deployment

The deployment of Service 8 is based on a **federated HBIM strategy**, implemented within **Autodesk Revit** and designed to support preventive conservation in real historic buildings. This service **integrates heterogeneous datasets into a single digital environment**, providing a **structured, semantic model capable of informing inspections, interventions, and long-term management strategies**.

The process follows a stepwise logic that begins with the **structured acquisition and enrichment** of three primary data sources:

- **Preliminary Documentation**, such as historical studies, architectural drawings, and conservation reports.

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- **2D/3D Geometric Data**, derived from laser scanning and material surveys.

Figure 71: Point cloud and HBIM overlay of the Monastery of Nuestra Señora del Prado. Partial modelling integrated within the full scan context.

- **Technical Inspection Data**, collected via digital forms and structured around a predefined inspection methodology (developed in WP3, Task 3.1).

All **inputs** are **processed and linked** into a federated HBIM model divided into four sub-models. The model is developed at **LOD 300-350** and aligned with **IFC export** rules to facilitate traceability, semantic coherence, and data interoperability. Each element of the model incorporates **alphanumeric attributes** (parameters) associated with one or more of the seven **information levels** defined in Service 8.

The diagram bellow illustrates how preliminary documentation, 2D/3D spatial data, and technical inspection records are integrated into a federated HBIM model. Each domain (Architecture, MEP, Pathologies, Maintenance) contributes to a **centralized, queryable environment that enables on-demand decision support based on building-specific data**.

Figure 72: Functional architecture of Service 8.

To ensure **flexibility and replicability**, the deployment approach **emphasizes modularity**. The HBIM project is structured in linked, discipline-specific files (.rvt), managed through a master coordination model that allows parallel work and controlled updates. Decision-support outputs (e.g., inspection priorities, maintenance schedules, risk analysis) are not delivered through a dedicated interface but are instead generated within the HBIM environment using built-in Revit tools (schedules, filters, views, parameter queries), **in line with the constraints and workflows of conservation professionals**.

Two pilot cases serve as proof-of-concept for this deployment:

Pilot 6, Monastery of Nuestra Señora del Prado (Spain): A highly complex fundamentally baroque structure with multiple construction phases and architectural styles requiring bespoke families and intensive semantic enrichment, including historical, pathological, and maintenance data.

Pilot 5, Residential Building in Gdynia (Poland): A modern, multi-unit residential structure with simpler geometry but greater operational challenges, particularly regarding stakeholder coordination and historical data gaps.

In both cases, **the HBIM deployment is tailored** to reflect each building's specific configuration, conservation needs, and user constraints, ensuring meaningful implementation beyond the prototype stage.

Additionally, core aspects of this methodology, semantic layers, parameter logic, and maintenance-oriented design, are consistent with established frameworks such as those developed by Historic England (2017). Similar principles are also reflected in research by Jordán Palomar (2019), who proposes a structured HBIM-based protocol for managing heritage-building interventions, with emphasis on information traceability and procedural standardisation.

5.2. s.9 GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance

5.2.1. Service overview

The service offers a comprehensive **GIS-based solution for the sustainable maintenance of cultural heritage CH buildings**. By combining geospatial analytics and unsupervised machine learning, the service enables municipalities and stakeholders to explore architectural typologies, identify patterns, and support data-driven renovation strategies. The core objective is to group CH buildings based on shared morphological and structural features, facilitating scalable interventions that improve energy performance, comfort, and sustainability without compromising historical identity.

The service is deployed through an **interactive web-based application** that displays categorized building clusters on a map, enriched with detailed feature metadata for each structure. It will be applied to pilot sites in **Greece (Pilot 3)** and **Sweden (Pilot 7)** and will be replicated in **Latvia (Pilot 4)**.

5.2.2. Input & output data

The service operates based on a structured flow of input, processing, and output data, ensuring the reliable analysis and categorization of cultural heritage buildings in support of sustainable maintenance strategies.

Input Data

The input data primarily consists of geospatial and architectural information collected from national heritage repositories and municipal sources in each participating city:

- **Athens:** Building records were obtained from the [National Archive of Monuments](#) and the Contemporary Monuments Database of the [National Hellenic Research Foundation](#).
- **Visby:** Data were sourced from the Swedish National Heritage Board ([Riksantikvarieämbetet](#)).
- **Riga:** Data sources are being finalized and will be integrated in the next release.

For each listed building, detailed attributes were documented under a unified schema, including:

- Construction year
- Architectural style
- Original and current use
- Construction materials
- Number of floors
- Renovation status
- Structural and architectural elements
- Decorative features
- Balconies and facade openings

These features provide the basis for clustering buildings with similar characteristics.

Output Data

The processed outputs of the system include:

- **Building clusters:** Groups of buildings with shared typological traits, generated using unsupervised learning (k-modes).
- **An interactive map interface:** Visual representation of the clusters and individual building characteristics, enabling:
 - Color-coded identification of clusters
 - Filtering by building feature or cluster
 - Search by address or district
- **Feature-level metadata:** For each building, detailed descriptive information is accessible through the map interface.

These outputs support strategic decisions regarding heritage preservation, retrofitting plans, and cross-city comparisons of architectural typologies.

5.2.3. Updated architecture & technical specification

For the creation of the thematic interactive maps, a suite of Esri technologies (one of the world's leading suppliers of GIS software) licensed under the National Technical University of Athens was employed. ArcGIS Pro 3.4, as a 64-bit desktop GIS software, utilizes a multi-threaded architecture that supports complex geospatial analysis and high-quality 2D/3D map visualisation. It seamlessly integrates with ArcGIS Online, Esri's cloud-based SaaS platform, under the NTUA cloud server, which provides scalable web-based mapping, data hosting, and sharing capabilities through RESTful services. To build dynamic, user-friendly applications, ArcGIS Experience Builder, a web app development tool built on React and the ArcGIS API for JavaScript was used, offering modular, widget-based customization for responsive design. Lastly, ArcGIS StoryMaps was incorporated, which blends interactive maps with narrative text and multimedia, allowing for compelling spatial storytelling through a user-friendly, template-driven interface connected directly to ArcGIS Online-hosted content.

5.2.4. Implementation: second technology release

ArcGIS Pro 3.4 is used as a desktop GIS tool, while ArcGIS online and ArcGIS StoryMaps for the presentation and dissemination of the results. Through ArcGIS Pro, the input data was georeferenced and implemented in dynamic maps, through ArcGIS Pro tools. For each pilot case, a shapefile .shp feature layer was created, including all essential information in dedicated attribute tables. The feature layers were then exported to custom made basemaps on the ArcGIS Online NTUA's server, which were created through the combination of designer tools of ArcGIS online and basemaps of Living Atlas. The result basemap, integrates several aesthetic components and the Open Street Map (OSM) building footprints and typology names (streets names, municipalities, cities, regions etc.). The available buildings of the INHERIT pilots, were integrated in the INHERIT custom basemap, as interactive feature layers and were classified and colour coded through the Classify attribute. Finally, a custom, friendly user interface was created, through ArcGIS Experience builder, with dedicated filters regarding architectural and structural features, for the showcase of the pilot buildings. For each pilot, a dedicated map was created, aligned with the INHERIT requirements. The pilot maps were integrated into a single ArcGIS StoryMap for presentation of the results and the dissemination of the service. In the second release, the Athens and Visby pilots were included.

5.2.4.1. Backend implementation

Although no dedicated backend service has been deployed, a set of standalone Python scripts is responsible for all data preprocessing and clustering preparation tasks. More specifically:

Raw input data are collected from national cultural heritage repositories.

Descriptive architectural and structural attributes, such as construction materials, decorative features, and building use, are transformed from textual to categorical form (i.e., encoded), ensuring compatibility with machine learning models.

These structured datasets are then processed using the k-modes clustering algorithm, which is optimized for categorical data and ideal for identifying building typologies based on shared characteristics.

The resulting CSV files are then used as input for the GIS-based tools and visualised within the interactive web application.

5.2.4.2. Frontend implementation

- **Introduction, Methodology, and Guidelines**

All pilots share the three explanatory chapters in the storyline – Introduction, Methodology, and Guidelines. The Introduction describes the high-level concept of the tool, the Methodology focuses on the data collection and treatment, and the Guidelines provide a detailed description of the Pilot Maps chapters below, features, and filters.

Figure 73: The starting chapter of the storyline in s.9.

- **Pilot Maps**

Each pilot features a dedicated interactive map, centred on its geographical location. All relevant heritage buildings are visualised and color-coded based on cluster membership, which is determined through an unsupervised clustering algorithm tailored to each city's dataset.

A cluster legend is provided to help interpret group characteristics. By selecting a building, users can access its full attribute profile, which appears both in a pop-up and in a side panel. This includes detailed architectural and structural information, along with direct links to the building's official heritage registry and a photo reference. Furthermore, dynamic filters allow users to refine their view by applying specific architectural or functional criteria. The entire interface is also accessible in full-screen mode for enhanced map navigation.

Figure 74: Screenshot of the GIS map chapter for the Athens pilot in s.9.

5.2.5. Deployment

The StoryMap is hosted in *storymaps.archgis* domain and can be accessed following [this link](#). Map data is loaded via .csv from the backend to the frontend, while the rest of the chapters are static.

5.3. s.10 Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios

5.3.1. Service overview

The *Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios* (s.10) service provides a spatial risk assessment tool designed to evaluate how climate change may impact CH buildings and surrounding urban areas. It supports heritage managers, urban planners, and municipal climate adaptation officers in understanding both current and future risk exposure, primarily at the building level within the city scale.

The service operationalises the IPCC AR6 risk framework, in which **risk** results from the interaction of three core components: **hazard, exposure, and vulnerability**. While the broader framework also recognises the role of response (i.e., adaptation or mitigation actions, see Figure 75) in influencing future risk, the s.10 focuses on the core components that determine current and projected risk

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levels. According to the IPCC, climate risk is “*the potential for adverse consequences for human or ecological systems*”, emerging from the *dynamic interactions between climate-related hazards, the exposure of assets or populations, and their vulnerability to harm* (IPCC, 2023). This framing enables the service to deliver risk assessments that are both spatially specific and socially relevant.

Figure 75: Components of climate risk as defined in IPCC AR6

s.10 focuses on three key climate-related hazards:

- **Extreme heat**
- **Flooding**
- **Strong wind**

In the service, each hazard can be explored under both **current and projected climate conditions**, with scenario-based simulations using **SSP245** and **SSP585** for two target timeframes: **2050** and **2070**.

Key functionalities include (see workflow in Figure 76):

- An **interactive web tool** that allows users to select their pilot city, choose a hazard, and visualise risk levels on colour-coded maps.
- The ability to **compare baseline (historical) risk conditions** with future climate scenarios.
- **Indicator-based visualisations** that show how risk is influenced by hazard probability of exceedance, exposure (e.g., building density, typology), and vulnerability (e.g., CH status, buildings sensitivities, and socioeconomic characteristics).

Figure 76: s.10 workflow diagram (depicting user flow from hazard selection to risk map visualisation under different scenarios)

The service is demonstrated in three pilot cities:

- **Visby, Sweden** (*UNESCO World Heritage Site*) – Pilot 7
- **Jastrebarsko, Croatia** – Pilot 1
- **Izmir, Turkey** (*early replicator*) – Pilot 8

Overall, the service is designed to support **climate-resilient conservation planning**, targeted adaptation measures, and prioritisation of investments in vulnerable heritage assets. It directly contributes to **Pillar 3** of the INHERIT Assessment Framework: *Resilience to climate and human-made hazards*.

5.3.2. Input & output data

The service relies on multiple data sources to generate spatially explicit risk layers and visualisations for each hazard. These data enable the calculation of hazard probability, exposure patterns, and vulnerability indicators specific to cultural heritage buildings. Due to limitations in socioeconomic data across pilots, the vulnerability layer is primarily modelled through physical and typological characteristics of heritage buildings.

Input data are structured into three main layers, as depicted in Table 18.

Risk component	Input data	Details
Hazard (probability of exceedance)	Historical weather data	From local stations (e.g., temperature, rainfall, wind)
	Climate projections	SSP245 and SSP585 for 2050 and 2070, derived from Copernicus C3S (e.g., CMIP6, CORDEX)
	Copernicus climate services	ERA5 reanalysis data, used for baseline calibration

Risk component	Input data	Details
Exposure	Urban sensor data (if available)	For microclimate refinement
	Building geometries	Footprints or polygons, ideally at building level
	Year of construction	To assess building age and degradation potential and to estimate different building characteristics
	Use/ typology	Residential, institutional, etc.
Vulnerability	Population (optional)	Used if available, relevant at sub-city level (i.e., census tract, district or neighbourhood)
	CH status	Listed, UNESCO or protected buildings
	Building materials and typology	Used to infer hazard sensitivity
	Indoor comfort capacity	Relevant for heat risk (e.g., passive cooling)
	Socioeconomic indicators (if available)	Used only if pilots provide them, not core to the service

Table 18: Overview of input data used in the s.10 Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios service

The **granularity of the risk assessment** depends on data availability and resolution of input data. Where building-level data are provided, the outputs are highly detailed.

The main outputs of the s.10 are spatial risk visualisation and qualitative indicators tailored to support local adaptation planning and prioritisation. These include those in Table 19.

Output type	Description
Risk maps	Hazard-specific colour-coded maps (historical and future)
Component layers	Visualisation of exposure, hazard and vulnerability
Scenario comparison	Maps and graphs showing changes under SSP245 and SSP585 in future timeframes
Interactive platform output	Web-based interface for scenario selection and map exploration

Table 19: Overview of output data from the s.10 Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios service

These outputs are designed to inform pilot cities' adaptation priorities and facilitate integration of climate risk considerations into heritage planning processes.

5.3.3. Updated architecture & technical specification

The architecture of the s.10 is designed as a **modular, data-driven pipeline**, enabling risk assessment for heritage under current and future climate scenarios. The service integrates multiple datasets (spatial, climate, and building-level) into a central processing engine that calculates risk indicators and serves the results through an interactive web-based interface.

The architecture is structured into three core layers: **database layer**, **logic layer**, and **presentation layer**, as shown in Figure 77.

Figure 77: Updated architecture of the s.10 (showing components for data ingestion, processing and web-based visualisation)

Data layer

This layer handles the ingestion and storage of all relevant data types:

- **Geospatial data:** building geometries, city/district boundaries, heritage building registries
- **Climate datasets:** Copernicus C3S services (e.g., ERA5 for historical baseline; CMIP6/SSP scenarios for projections) and data postprocessed from these
- **Building metadata:** year of construction, typology, comfort-related variables
- **Socioeconomic data:** optional and included only where available (e.g., population, income, age distribution)

Logic layer

This is the computational core of the service. It includes:

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- **Hazard probability modules**, built from historical weather records and climate projections
- **Exposure and vulnerability layer generation**, using building data and typological indicators
- **Risk calculation algorithm**, implementing the IPCC AR6 formula: $Risk = Hazard \times Exposure \times Vulnerability$
- **Downscaling module**, enabling adaptation of coarse-resolution climate data to city or building scale

All computations are scenario-sensitive, allowing users to switch between **SSP245** and **SSP585** and explore risk projections for **2050** and **2070**.

Presentation layer

The frontend of the service is a web-based user interface, developed to provide:

- **Hazard and scenario selection**: user input to define pilot site, hazard type, SSP scenario, and timeframe
- **Risk assessment maps**: colour-coded visualisations of overall risk, with the ability to explore individual layers of hazard probability, exposure and vulnerability
- **Scenario comparison tool**: to compare baseline vs. future risk conditions

The visualisation interface is implemented using **web GIS technologies** (e.g., Leaflet), which render interactive raster or vector maps based on the outputs from the logic layer.

5.3.4. Implementation: second technology release

The second technology release of the s.10 focuses on consolidating the core backend components and advancing the development of the interactive frontend interface. This release is a stepping stone towards full integration of all hazard types, scenario simulations, and visualisation layers, with emphasis on usability, modularity, and adaptability to pilot-specific data availability.

5.3.4.1. Backend implementation

The backend is structured as a modular pipeline that integrates input data sources, processes them through the risk logic framework, and prepares the outputs for visualisation. In this second release, the following backend components have been implemented or are under active development:

- **Data ingestion and processing modules**: harmonisation scripts for loading and validating geospatial, climate and building data have been implemented. These modules include unit conversion, georeferencing and quality checks, tailored to the structure of available pilot datasets.
- **Hazard-specific submodules**: processing pipelines for hazard probability layers are being developed separately for each hazard (extreme heat, flooding, strong wind). At present, components for individual hazard layers are in place, though full risk calculation per hazard is still under integration.

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- **Exposure and vulnerability later generation:** backend logic for generating building-level exposure and vulnerability indicators is implemented. This includes mapping of typology, year of construction, CH status and comfort capacity. Where data are missing, default or inferred values can be used based on pilot typologies.
- **Scenario module (under integration):** support for scenario-based data processing (SSP245 and SSP585 for 2050 and 2070) is being integrated, and maps will be generated to allow the selection of scenario-based layers.
- **Risk computation logic:** the algorithm implementing $Risk = Hazard \times Exposure \times Vulnerability$ is structured and tested independently, but full integration across all layers and hazards is ongoing. Computation currently operates on pilot subsets for testing and debugging.

All backend components are being developed in Python, with a focus on modularity and reusability across different pilot contexts (present and future). Outputs are structured as georeferenced raster or vector layers

5.3.4.2. Frontend implementation

The frontend of the s.10 has been implemented as a modular, **map-based web interface**, tailored for use by pilot cities and later on by the replicator. It is designed to offer a streamlined user journey from hazard and scenario selection to interactive visualisation of risk and component indicators.

The user interface enables the selection of a pilot city and a hazard (flooding, extreme heat, or strong winds), as well as the simulation of future scenarios. Figure 78 presents the interface for hazard and risk layer selection, including intuitive buttons and icons to support user interaction.

Figure 78: User interface for hazard and risk layers selection (mock-up)

Risk outputs are displayed as colour-coded maps, allowing users to visualise **building-level risk** levels. For example, Figure 79 shows flooding risk in Visby, based on historical data, while Figure 80 presents the exposure layer for Jastrebarsko, an individual component of the risk equation.

Figure 79: Risk map visualisation for flooding in Visby, Sweden (mock-up)

Figure 80: Exposure component of flooding risk in Jastrebarsko, Croatia (mock-up)

To support interpretation of hazard-specific parameters, the interface includes pop-up windows displaying threshold exceedance curves in graphical format. Unlike exposure and vulnerability, which vary spatially across the urban area (different building characteristics and potentially

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variations in population density or other socioeconomic data at the district level or similar), the **probability of exceedance** does not present significant intra-urban variability. Representing it as a map would result in a uniform visualisation, offering limited insight. Therefore, it is presented as a graph summarising city-wide statistical behaviour, helping users understand the climate thresholds that define high-risk conditions. Importantly, the probability of exceedance is the only risk component that varies under future climate scenarios in the s.10. Exposure and vulnerability layers are assumed static in the simulations, while hazard intensity (probability) is dynamically modified based on SSP245 and SSP585 projections. Figure 81 and Figure 82 illustrate the exceedance probability curves for extreme heat in Jastrebarsko and strong winds in Visby, respectively.

Figure 81: Probability of exceedance for extreme heat in Jastrebarsko, Croatia (mock-up)

Figure 82: Probability of exceedance for strong winds in Visby, Sweden (mock-up)

A dedicated panel supports the simulation of future scenarios (see Figure 83), allowing users to define hazard type, SSP scenario (SSP245 and SSP585), and timeframe (2050 and 2070). This functionality is central to the service’s ability to support climate adaptation planning.

Figure 83: Future scenario simulation panel (mock-up)

5.3.5. Deployment

s.10 is being deployed first in the pilot cities of **Visby (Sweden)** and **Jastrebarsko (Croatia)**, and will subsequently be adapted for replication in **Izmir (Turkey)** as an early replicator. The deployment strategy involves a modular and progressive integration with local data systems and end users, ensuring the service’s functionalities are tailored to pilot-specific conditions and stakeholder needs.

Deployment to the pilots is enabled via the **web-based interface**, which allows end users to access the tool without local installation. The application follows INHERIT’s centralised service architecture, and is protected via secure login using the shared authentication system (see Figure 84). Local stakeholders, such as heritage managers, city planners, and climate adaptation officers, can explore historical climate risk maps and simulate risk evolution under different SSPs to visualise scenario-based risk maps and navigate risk component layers for further planning integration.

Figure 84: Login screen for accessing the service 10 (mock-up)

The pilot cities have actively contributed to the deployment phase by providing key building-level input data (e.g., geometries) and giving feedback on interface usability. This co-creation process ensures alignment between service capabilities and pilot-specific planning contexts. Based on this feedback, the service also integrates features such as graphical pop-ups for interpreting climate hazard thresholds, rather than using maps, due to the lack of intra-urban variability in hazard exceedance probability, which would render spatial maps redundant.

Importantly, the hazard layer (probability of exceedance) is the only dynamic component in the risk formula under climate scenario simulations. Exposure and vulnerability layers are treated as static, given current limitations in simulating future urban changes in urban form or social vulnerability at high spatial resolution. This design choice enhances interpretability and ensures consistency across risk scenarios, while maintaining focus on climate-driven changes.

For **potential replicators**, the service is designed to be scalable and data-flexible. By relying on standard data formats (e.g., GeoJSON, raster grids), open data (e.g., OSM) and open climate

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datasets (e.g., Copernicus C3S), it can be adapted to other European cities, provided that minimum input data are available. Deployment for replicators will follow a similar structure as the pilots, beginning with data preparation and validation, followed by interface customisation and stakeholder onboarding (see Figure 85).

Figure 85: City selection interface for deployment in pilot cities (mock-up)

Conclusions

This second deliverable (D4.2) presents the evolved architecture and updated implementation status of the INHERIT services, reflecting the progress made since the first development cycle documented in D4.1. It captures the iterative improvements and functional enhancements applied to the initial service components, consolidating the platform's ability to support robust, scalable, and interoperable data-driven operations.

Building upon the architectural foundation established in D4.1, this deliverable outlines how the services have matured—technically and conceptually—to better address the INHERIT's core objectives. Key updates include the refinement of the data integration and storage mechanisms, the extension of real-time data offering, the improvements in the advanced user-facing tools, and the integration of these services with the data management platform.

As we move toward the next phase and final phase of the project, the results of this deliverable form a stable and mature foundation upon which final refinements and validations will be performed. The upcoming deliverable will focus on full-scale deployment, validation in pilot environments, and the final alignment of services with user needs and project KPIs.

In conclusion, this deliverable demonstrates the INHERIT platform's transition from early prototypes to a more cohesive and functional ecosystem, reinforcing the project's commitment to delivering a decision support infrastructure capable of preserving and managing Europe's cultural heritage in the face of complex environmental and societal challenges.

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Annex I: H-BIM Input Data Collection

This annex compiles the technical documentation and methodological decisions involved in the **scan-to-HBIM workflows** developed for Pilot 5: Residential Building in Gdynia (Poland) and Pilot 6: Monastery of Nuestra Señora del Prado (Spain). These records ensure that both the geometric and semantic inputs used **to support Service 8 are accurate, consistent, and verifiable**.

Gathering reliable information for HBIM modelling is particularly complex in the context of heritage buildings, where understanding the construction systems, historical evolution, and conservation state of the asset requires a multi-source and multidisciplinary approach. In these cases, laser scanning and modelling are only part of the process: archival research, technical inspections, and stakeholder consultation are equally crucial to produce a meaningful, data-rich model.

In both pilots, a common technical framework was applied, including:

Use of high-precision laser scanning to capture the geometry of the asset.

Systematic registration, cleaning, and verification of the point cloud datasets.

Creation of HBIM models with parametric elements at LOD 300–350.

Structuring of models into federated submodels and information levels aligned with Service 8's data model.

In the case of Pilot 6 (Valladolid), additional efforts were made to reinforce semantic quality and integrate multiple knowledge domains. A series of targeted technical meetings were held with:

- Public maintenance staff from the Regional Government of Castilla y León, to document existing systems, conservation symptoms, and intervention history.
- The building's IT manager, to enable the installation of environmental sensors for indoor air quality monitoring.
- Experts in architecture, art history, and heritage conservation, to gather historical studies, construction records, and cultural value documentation.

In the case of Pilot 5 (Gdynia), the information gathering process presented specific challenges due to the fragmented ownership structure—with one private owner per apartment—and the limited availability of historical documentation. The building, a residential block from the early 20th century, has undergone numerous undocumented modifications over time, which complicates both the interpretation of its construction systems and the reconstruction of its maintenance history.

Despite these limitations, the HBIM model was developed using high-resolution laser scanning, complemented by in situ observations and partial information provided by residents. The modelling process focused on reconstructing the geometric and constructive logic of the building envelope, interior partitions, and accessible installations, while identifying areas of uncertainty or missing data for future inspection or stakeholder input.

PILOT 5: Residential Building in Gdynia, Poland

1- General Information

Building Coordinates	54.52, 18.53
Type of building	Residential
Scanning Start and End Date	14.03.2024
Photo(s)	

2- Laser Scanning Data	
Laser Scanner Model	Leica RTC360
Manufacture	Leica
Resolution Used	6mm/10m
Scanner Accuracy	1.9mm/10m
Maximum Scanning Distance	130m
Environmental condition During Scanning	Good weather conditions
Total Scanning Duration	4h
Number of Scan Positions	82
Overlap Between Scans	65%
Strength	48%
Error	2.59mm
Point Cloud Export Format	XYZ and RCP
Scanning Observation (issues detected)	

3- Point Cloud Processing	
Software Used for Scan Registration	Leica Register 360
Software Used for Cleaning and Processing the Cloud	Leica Register 360
Cleaning and Filtering Methods Applied	Removing Mixed-Pixel points, ambiguous points, intensity-overloaded points, Manually removing noises
Number of Points in Original Cloud	2 277 515 015
Number of points After Cleaning	1 704 953 889
Point Cloud Quality Verification	
Final Cloud Format for Modelling	RCP and XYZ
Processing Observations (issues detected)	
Picture(s)	

4- HBIM Model Creation (work in progress)	
Software Used for HBIM modelling	Autodesk Revit
Level of Detail (LOD) of the Model	LOD300 – LOD350
Model planning to be useful for service 8 development	-
Parametric Elements Used	Walls, windows, doors, roofs, floors, stairs, wall foundations, ceilings, balustrades
Semantic information (Non-Geometric) Associated with the pilot characteristics	Historical data, materials and conservation data, maintenance and inspections information
H-BIM Model observation (Hazards)	Lack of information on the current status of inaccessible spaces in the building.
Picture(s)	

PILOT 6: Monastery of Nuestra Señora del Prado in Valladolid, Spain.

1- General Information

D4.2 – Second Wave of INHERIT Decision Support Services

Building Coordinates	41.64088182222402, -4.745781503089989
Type of building	Office
Scanning Start and End Date	From 2024/07/29 to 2024/09/02 + extra 2025/03/20
Photo(s)	

2- Laser Scanning Data

Laser Scanner Model	BLK 360 G1
Manufacture	Leica Geosystems
Resolution Used	360.000 points per second
Scanner Accuracy	4 mm
Maximum Scanning Distance	60 m

D4.2 – Second Wave of INHERIT Decision Support Services

Environmental condition During Scanning	Sunny day
Total Scanning Duration	20 h
Number of Scan Positions	40 scan positions (church + cloister) + 10 extra scan positions (Sacristy + façade)
Overlap Between Scans	48%
Strength	68%
Error	<0.005 m
Point Cloud Export Format	.rcp & .pts
Scanning Observation (issues detected)	Scanning was limited by the large number of employees working. Access to the building was also complicated by restrictions due to its high level of security as the headquarters of the regional government.

3- Point Cloud Processing

Software Used for Scan Registration	Leica Cyclone REGISTER 360 (BLK Edition)
Software Used for Cleaning and Processing the Cloud	Autodesk ReCap Pro; CloudCompare
Cleaning and Filtering Methods Applied	Apply SOR Filter, then Radius Filter, followed by Subsampling, and finally Merge the point clouds.

D4.2 – Second Wave of INHERIT Decision Support Services

Number of Points in Original Cloud	Approximately 425 million points
Number of points After Cleaning	Reduced to 297 million points
Point Cloud Quality Verification	Apply SOR Filter, then Radius Filter, followed by Subsampling, and finally Merge the point clouds.
Final Cloud Format for Modelling	.rcp & .pts
Processing Observations (issues detected)	High reflectivity in glazed areas generated some noise. Noise under desks and ceilings manually removed.
Picture(s)	<p>The screenshot shows the Cyclone REGISTER 360 (BIM Edition) interface. The main window displays a point cloud of a large, vaulted interior space, likely a monastery. A red box highlights a specific area labeled 'Tubo de conjunto'. The right-hand panel shows the 'Asistente' (Assistant) with 'Propiedades' (Properties) for 'SiteMap 1-1', listing statistics such as 'Número de conjuntos: 1', 'Número de escaneos: 50', 'Número de enlases: 162', 'Número de dianas: 1', and 'Número de puntos: 1.090.818.8'. Below this, there are fields for 'Activo', 'Nombre', and 'Escaneo', along with 'Editar' and 'Eliminar' buttons. The bottom of the panel shows 'Imagen' fields for 'Recurso' and 'Origen'.</p>

4- HBIM Model Creation (work in progress)

D4.2 – Second Wave of INHERIT Decision Support Services

Software Used for HBIM modelling	Autodesk Revit 2023
Level of Detail (LOD) of the Model	LOD300 – LOD350
Model planning to be useful for service 8 development	Federated HBIM model structured through thematic sub-models (Architecture, MEP, Pathologies, and Maintenance), aligned with the categories and terminology defined in the historical buildings technical inspection methodology. The model is intended to support preventive maintenance by integrating geometric, material, and diagnostic information in a semantically enriched environment.
Parametric Elements Used	Walls, vaults, arches, columns, windows, stairs, and slabs, all modelled as custom parametric families adapted in situ. Due to the historical and geometric complexity of the building, standard Revit families were not suitable and bespoke elements were created based on point cloud data.
Semantic information (Non-Geometric) Associated with the pilot characteristics	Element type, material, construction period, use, pathology tags, inspection data, historical references
H-BIM Model observation (Hazards)	The large size and irregularity of historical vaults required custom modelling. Laser shadows in cornices and at the springing points of arches required manual adjustments during modelling.

To complement the technical documentation presented in this annex, it is important to highlight that the definition of inspection parameters and typologies within Service 8 is grounded in the criteria developed under Deliverable D3.2: Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework. Specifically, Annex 1 of D3.2 provides a detailed breakdown of pathological symptoms, lesion types, inspection methods, and review frequencies for key building components, including structures, façades, installations, and safety systems.

This annex, developed with input from expert partners in Spain and Poland, has informed the design of both the inspection methodology and the semantic structure of the HBIM models documented herein.

Annex II: IFC 4 Entities Relevant to Preventive Maintenance Modelling

IFC Entity	Description
IfcWall	Wall element, structural or non-structural
IfcSlab	Flat horizontal or inclined building element (floor, roof, etc.)
IfcColumn	Vertical structural element, often load-bearing
IfcBeam	Horizontal structural element supporting loads
IfcDoor	Opening with function of access
IfcWindow	Framed opening for light or ventilation
IfcStair	Staircase element
IfcRoof	Covering element of a building
IfcCovering	Layer or finish applied to a surface (e.g., plaster, paint)
IfcSpace	Volume representing a functional area (room, void)

IfcOpeningElement	Opening in building elements (e.g., recess, void)
IfcBuildingElementProxy	Generic element without a specific IFC class
IfcDistributionElement	General MEP element
IfcFlowSegment	Segment of a flow system (duct, pipe, cable tray)
IfcFlowTerminal	End-point device in a distribution system (e.g., sink, radiator)
IfcFlowController	Control device in a system (e.g., valve, switch)
IfcFlowFitting	Junction or transition element in a flow system
IfcSystem	Logical grouping of MEP components
IfcCableCarrierSegment	Cable trays or conduits
IfcElectricDistributionBoard	Distribution board for electrical systems
IfcAnnotation	Non-physical graphical or symbolic representation
IfcSurfaceFeature	Feature applied to the surface of a building element (e.g., crack)
IfcDocumentReference	External document linked to elements (e.g., report, image)

IfcExternalInformation	Reference to external databases or metadata
IfcTask	Planned activity or intervention (maintenance, inspection)
IfcTaskTime	Scheduling information for a task
IfcTaskTimeRecurring	Recurring schedule for tasks
IfcWorkControl	Management and control object for work processes
IfcActor	Person or organization associated with actions
IfcSensor	Monitoring device that measures conditions (e.g., humidity, CO ₂)
IfcPerformanceHistory	Log of performance data over time
IfcMaintenanceRecord	Record of performed maintenance actions (custom extension in some tools)